

ASSESSMENT OF REGULATORY REQUIREMENTS AND CONSTRAINTS FOR A COMBINED EXTRACTION OF HEAT AND MINERALS - WITH COUNTRY OVERVIEWS -

Summary:

Every project for the extraction of minerals has to be subject to a PESTEL (political, environmental, societal, technological, economic, legal) analysis to assess its viability. The combined extraction of heat and minerals is no exception even though it would not be a classical mining. This report, presents an assessment of the regulatory schemes in a comprehensive selection of European countries plus Turkey. This is document is an extract from CRM-geothermal Deliverable 4.1.

Authors:

W. Eberhard Falck, INTRAW
Vitor Correia, INTRAW

Recommended citation: Falck, W. E. & Correia, V., Assessment of regulatory requirements and constraints for a combined extraction of heat and minerals – with country overviews, Zenodo, 2025, DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.17621225](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17621225)

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or HADEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Table of contents	2
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	4
1 Objectives	5
2 Method and caveats	5
3 Geothermal energy system regulatory framework	6
3.1 Current opinions in the literature.....	6
3.2 Definition and classification of geothermal energy	7
3.3 Geothermal resource ownership	8
3.4 Geothermal energy licensing system	8
3.5 Regulatory costs/License fees/Royalties	9
3.6 Standards and Codes.....	9
4 Relevant European regulations	10
4.1 Environmental and extractive industries related regulations.....	10
4.2 Regulations on Occupational Safety and Health (OSH)	13
5 Selected European states’ legislation and policies.....	15
6 Regulatory challenges to permitting of combined extraction projects.....	16
7 Summary and conclusions	17
8 References.....	18
Appendix 1 - References to EU Regulations.....	20
Appendix 2 – Country regulatory systems for combined extraction.....	27
8.1 Austria.....	27
8.2 Belgium.....	28
8.3 Bulgaria.....	29
8.4 Croatia.....	29
8.5 Cyprus.....	30
8.6 Czechia.....	31
8.7 Denmark.....	31
8.8 Estonia	32
8.9 Finland	32
8.10 France	33
8.11 Germany	34
8.12 Greece.....	35
8.13 Hungary	35
8.14 Iceland.....	36
8.15 Ireland.....	37
8.16 Italy.....	37
8.17 Latvia.....	38
8.18 Lithuania	39
8.19 Luxembourg	39
8.20 Malta	40
8.21 The Netherlands	40
8.22 Poland.....	41
8.23 Portugal	42
8.24 Romania.....	43

8.25	Slovakia.....	44
8.26	Slovenia.....	45
8.27	Spain	45
8.28	Sweden	46
8.29	Turkey	47
8.30	UK.....	48

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The digital and energy transition in the European Union and worldwide implies an increasing need of raw materials that need to be mined, and provision of Critical Raw Materials (CRM) for the EU is usually linked to import dependency. A potential additional source of CRMs and an alternative to conventional mining could be the exploitation of geothermal reservoirs, as geothermal brines often contain high concentrations of metal ions. The EU-funded 'CRM-geothermal' project aims to open up the potentially huge untapped resource of raw materials from geothermal fluids and provide operators and investors with information needed to assess the viability of the approach of co-extraction heat and minerals from geothermal fluids.

Every project for the extraction of minerals has to be subject to a PESTEL (political, environmental, societal, technological, economic, legal) analysis to assess its viability. The combined extraction of heat and minerals is no exception even though it would not be a classical mining project with respect to the impacts and legacies it may create.

The data for a PESTEL assessment are completed by an assessment of the regulatory schemes across European countries plus Turkey. This report presents an overview over relevant regulations and permitting practices. It also details the countries' regulatory systems. However, in the majority of countries no specific regulations for combined extraction exist yet. It is concluded that in practice, the regulatory treatment of a given project would depend on what the primary objective of the project is: extraction of heat or extraction of metal value.

This document is an extract from CRM-geothermal Deliverable 4.1: Falck, W. E. & Correia, V., The Horizon Europe CRM-geothermal project: Deliverable 4.1 – ESG due diligence of the combined extraction of CRMs and energy, incl. UNFC/UNRMS compatible reporting and policy recommendation, Zenodo, 2025, DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.17235755](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17235755).

1 OBJECTIVES

The EU-funded ‘CRM-geothermal’ project aims to open up a potentially huge untapped resource of critical raw materials (CRM) that can be extracted from geothermal fluids. Combined extraction of heat and minerals maximises returns on investment for geothermal plants, minimises environmental impact and enables domestic supplies of CRM. The objective of the CRM-geothermal project is to provide the necessary information that would help to deploy the combined extraction of heat and minerals as a solution to help Europe fulfil the strategic objectives of the EU Green Deal and the Agenda for Sustainable Development.

Every project for the extraction of minerals has to be subject to a PESTEL (political, environmental, societal, technological, economic, legal) analysis to assess its viability. While much of the work in CRM-geothermal project is concerned with the development of efficient technologies for the extraction of critical raw materials (CRM; CRMA, 2024) from geothermal fluids, Work-Package 4 of this project focused on the other aspects of a PESTEL assessment.

The **objective of the PESTEL assessments** is to demonstrate that extraction is not only technically feasible (T), but that it is environmentally benign (E), is acceptable to the local communities (S), makes economic sense (E), and can be carried out in line with the applicable legal framework (L).

This report concentrates on the legal framework. It discusses the in most jurisdictions yet uncharted territories of regulating combined extraction projects. We aim to provide an overview over the regulatory framework for geothermal energy systems and introduce relevant European regulations. **Appendix 1** lists pertinent EU legal acts, while a detailed assessment of pertinent EU Member State legislation provided in **Appendix 2**.

2 METHOD AND CAVEATS

The combined extraction of minerals and heat is likely subject to a complex regulatory regime in the various EU Member States and adjacent countries.

In a first step for each country information about the regulatory regime applied in practice has been collated in order to understand the current situation (Appendix2).

The necessary regulatory mining licences and provisions (e.g. for extractive waste management) have been reviewed on the basis of *inter alia* the MinLex (2017) data for a range of European countries. However, the MinLex project was completed nearly ten years ago and regulations in the respective European countries since have evolved.

Another valuable source of information on the various regulatory regimes is the legal database (FAOLEX) maintained by the UN Food and Agricultural Organisation (FAO), which provides country profiles and also covers legislation on a variety of natural resources (<https://www.fao.org/faolex/country-profiles/en/>). In many cases English translations of the respective acts are available. While FAOLEX may not be completely up-to-date, it provides a valuable starting point for targeted searches on the Internet.

These reviews were undertaken in the course of the project, cognisant of the fact that regulatory systems constantly evolve. Where a revision was known to be imminent, the country profiles (Appendix 2) were revisited in Spring 2025.

The dimension of extracting minerals then has been added to the dimension of heat extraction in order to understand in what way and by what regulations such extraction may be covered in a given country. These analyses allow to prepare future sites for the regulatory challenges, but also to point out certain regulatory pitfalls and shortcomings.

3 GEOTHERMAL ENERGY SYSTEM REGULATORY FRAMEWORK

3.1 CURRENT OPINIONS IN THE LITERATURE

A comprehensive review of the regulatory system for geothermal energy projects was undertaken for France, Germany and the Netherlands by Goodman et al. (2009). On this basis, they made recommendation for regulatory systems that covered:

- Legal Guidelines
 - Definition and classification of geothermal energy
 - Geothermal resource ownership
 - Geothermal energy licensing system
 - Simplify regulations and administrative procedures
 - Geothermal energy licensing authority
 - Geothermal resources inventory and statistics
- Financial Incentives Guidelines
 - Regulatory costs/License fees/Royalties
 - Developing financial incentives schemes
 - Notes on financial incentives parameters
- General Guidelines for Flanking/Supporting Measures
 - Education, Training, and Certification
 - Promotion of geothermal energy
 - Standards and Codes
 - Research and Development

The regulatory systems of Belgium, France, Hungary, Iceland, Italy, and Turkey for geothermal projects were described in detail in the course of the H2020 Project GEOENVIE (Valkering, P. et al. 2020). The assessment focused on energy harvesting and considers wastes generated, such as scales, not as extractive waste, but as industrial wastes covered by the respective regulations. However, once the objective is metal extraction, it is likely that the Extractive Waste Directive (CEU 2006a) will apply.

The number of reports and papers that are concerned with making recommendations for the improvement of the regulatory systems across Europe seems to indicate that there are still shortcomings. The need to streamline and simplify licensing procedures across Europe thus was recognised and respective proposals were made by e.g. Batini (2021).

A position paper by the European Geothermal Energy Council (EGEC 2022) indicates, that at EU level many of the above points have begun to be addressed, but that the current situation has not changed significantly yet. The complexity of licensing procedures was

noted: *“Geothermal energy is regulated by many entities and regulations, dealing with mining in the underground and the surface as an industrial application, but also for the environmental, water and energy regulations. As illustrated in the delegated acts on EU taxonomy, geothermal resource is combined with several engines: turbine for Combined heat and power plants, District heating and Cooling systems, Heat pumps, Underground Thermal Energy Storage. Each engine has additional regulations and technical standards.”* Combined extraction will add an additional layer to this and there is uncertainty as to which regulatory body will take the lead in a given country and for a given project.

EGEC (2022) also noted a lack of capacities and capabilities on the side of regulators. This is not unique to geothermal projects or combined extraction, but the decline in mining across most Member States has also led to a severe reduction in mining regulators’ staffing or their amalgamation with e.g. environmental regulators. As a result, many regulators do not have staff with knowledge in deep drilling technology, well completion, geothermal systems or mining in general, making them *de facto* incapable to assess and regulate adequately such projects. Large scale deployment of geothermal and combined extraction projects will require the rebuilding of adequate regulatory capacity. Poorly regulated projects can undermine public confidence in such projects. Where they still exist, regulators experienced in hydrocarbon drilling projects could be redeployed here.

It appears that shallow geothermal systems, with which combined extraction is not concerned, have found more attention, including the regulatory aspects with respect to water resources management. Rupprecht et al. (2017) for instance compare the regulatory systems for various central European countries.

It should be noted that the observations made by various geothermal energy stakeholders, such as the EGEC, concern both, shallow and deep geothermal systems. However, combined extraction would rather target deep geothermal systems than systems that may only reach down to a few tens of meters. The approaches for associated EIAs and assessing potential competitions, as well as the regulatory bodies involved are different. In shallow projects the mining regulators would not normally be involved in.

In the following, a number of the above points for which recommendations were formulated by Goodman et al. (CEU 2009) are taken up and their implications for combined extraction are discussed.

3.2 DEFINITION AND CLASSIFICATION OF GEOTHERMAL ENERGY

According to Directive 2009/28/EC (CEU 2009) *“geothermal energy means energy stored in form of heat beneath the surface of solid earth”*. Article 5 of this Directive stipulates *“... that the final energy output significantly exceeds the primary energy input required to drive the heat pumps.”*, which is a reference to a positive energy balance of the system concerned. Annex VII further specifies the mode of calculating the energy balance.

In combined extraction systems this can become an important economic and regulatory question, as the extraction system may shift the energy balance or make systems at the lower end of efficiency more attractive due to the added value of metal extraction.

3.3 GEOTHERMAL RESOURCE OWNERSHIP

At the time of the review by Goodman et al. (2009) there has been no uniform practice across the EU for treating the ownership of deep geothermal resources from a regulatory perspective, which was confirmed again by EGEC (2022). Applicable legislation could come from the realms of water resources, mining, or hydrocarbon extraction. Depending on the specific system set-up, the major difference can be, that actually very little mass is extracted permanently, if the cooled-down water is being re-injected (rather than released to surface water courses). Only the heat-content is extracted.

The way how ownership of subsurface resources is treated varies from Member State to Member State. In general, shallow resources, down to a few metres below ground, are the property of the landowner, while deeper resources are owned by the state. The state may give permission to exploit such resources to private enterprises. For this, fees and royalties are payable to the state (see below).

It appears that currently in many cases ‘heat’ is not treated as a resource, but only as a source of potential environmental impact. The underlying reasoning presumably is that it is considered to be inexhaustible due to the radioactive decay in the earth’s interior.

Resource ownership is also related to the possibility to delimit the extension of the resource below ground. In the case of geothermal and combined extraction projects, this is complicated by the fact that we are dealing with flows of heat or matter, rather than with a static mineral resource. Without an appropriate 3D hydraulic flow-model or reservoir model, it is difficult to assess from which volume a geothermal borehole extracts heat and matter. Useful guidance on this can be found in the way how hydrocarbon exploration concessions are delimited.

3.4 GEOTHERMAL ENERGY LICENSING SYSTEM

Given the regulatory uncertainties discussed in the previous section, it is clear that this also affects the licensing and permitting of geothermal or combined extraction projects. Major issues to be considered are potential resources use conflicts between deep geothermal systems and deep mining, water resources use that may affect regional flow patterns, carbon capture and storage systems, and hydrocarbon extraction, although the latter due to the limited onshore oil & gas exploitation in Europe and the progressive decarbonisation of our societies will become less of an issue.

It is important that licensing is based on a comprehensive system analysis that tries to understand how a project may impact the subsurface space and how other subsurface activities might influence in their turn the geothermal project.

While it is not very likely, that deep geothermal reservoirs would be used for drinking-water supply, use of shallower aquifers above may change flow-pattern and recharge rates, thus affecting the geothermal system. Water resources management considerations would also be relevant in case the produced waters were to be discharged into surface water courses, rather than being reinjected. The Water Framework Directive 2000/60/EC (CEU 2000) provides guidance in this respect. Some MSs have also established orders of precedence, such that water resources take precedence over mineral resources.

A systemic and modelling approach to licensing will help to understand the possible interference between geothermal energy systems and carbon capture and storage that may target similar deep formations. The risk is that injected CO₂ migrates towards geothermal projects and is brought to the surface again with the produced waters.

3.5 REGULATORY COSTS/LICENSE FEES/ROYALTIES

According to the discussion in Goodman et al. (2009), no clear and uniform approach across EU Member States is in place for determining any licensing fees or royalties.

The underlying assumption presumably is that ‘heat’ is not (yet) defined as a resource. The tacit assumption is also that ‘heat’ is a renewable resource that is replenished from deeper geological strata and, compared to the theoretical total heat contained in the earth and regenerated through radioactive decay, the amount extracted by humans will be negligible on a global scale. However, on a local or regional scale there may be depletion, depending on the heat conducting processes.

If, as in most relevant cases of deep geothermal systems, the produced waters would be re-injected in nearby boreholes, there will be little net water extraction that may fall under the respective water resources regulations and attract permitting fees.

However, the situation may be different for combined extraction, where metal value is removed permanently from the subsurface space for commercial purposes. In this case, one would expect, that license fees and royalties similar to those for conventional mining could be applied. One could argue for a significant discount compared to conventional mining, as some of these fees and royalties normally would be used for environmental remediation or compensation measures, which in the case of combined extraction are significantly lower or not even necessary. In addition, combined extraction occurs in conjunction with the strategic objective of supplying low-carbon footprint energy.

Likewise, the usual instruments to finance environmental remediation of mine sites, such as bonds, probably could be largely waived. The remedial effort would mainly concern the decommissioning of the surface installations. No significant amount of soil remediation would be expected. It should be noted, that none of the regulatory documents reviewed discusses these points explicitly. The amount of post-mining remediation needed would normally be determined on the basis of the Environmental Impact Assessment. In the case of combined extraction comparatively little impact is to be expected.

3.6 STANDARDS AND CODES

Geothermal energy projects have to adhere to the relevant EU and national standards (Goodman et al., 2009), including those on:

- Drilling safety procedures, cf. Directive 92/91/EEC (CEU 1992)
- Drilling equipment efficiency
- Borehole completion standards
- Environmental and groundwater protection
- Quality of borehole heat exchanger completion
- Manifolds and installation of surface equipment
- Sizing and design guidelines to ensure the sustainable and efficient operation
- Standards for individual system components

4 RELEVANT EUROPEAN REGULATIONS

4.1 ENVIRONMENTAL AND EXTRACTIVE INDUSTRIES RELATED REGULATIONS

A frequent motivation to develop regulatory instruments in the EU is to address environmental, individual human or societal risk and impacts. Thus, achieving compliance with these EU regulations and their national subsidiaries are a major driver for environmental, safety & health, and societal impact assessment for planned projects. These regulatory instruments may be complemented by policy instruments that typically have a more proactive function by steering economic and societal activities into directions perceived as being for instance more sustainable, such as the EU ‘Green Deal’ (European Commission 2019) or the EU Raw Materials Act (CRMA, 2024).

The EU Directives and other regulations have to be transposed into or homologated with national legislation, which then become the enforceable legal instruments at EU Member State level. Compliance with EU regulations cannot be directly enforced by the EU at levels below the national level. This is the obligation of the MSs through their respective regulatory systems.

Typically, EU regulatory instruments only give the broad outline of the issues to be considered and actions to be taken. They set objectives, rather than describe the implementation, which usually is covered by national laws, by-laws, regulations, and codes. There is, however, EU guidance on specific fields through the collection of BREFs (Best Available Techniques Reference Documents (for an overview of available documents see <https://eippcb.jrc.ec.europa.eu/reference>).

EU Directives relevant to the combined extraction come from a wide variety of policy-making and regulatory realms, such as the environment s.s., water and air emissions, waste management, resources and energy conservation, nature conservation, work-place safety & health, etc. Some years ago, the European Commission initiated a study to summarise policy and legal instruments relevant to mining on both, EU and national level (MinLex, 2017). This study produced a large collection of country fact-sheets (which are available from the EU Joint Research Centre’s Raw Materials Information System (RMIS, <https://rmis.jrc.ec.europa.eu/topic/legislation>):

1. **Internal market legislation:** eight items, including the principal Directives relevant to the topic of the MinLex project: Professional Qualifications Directive, Services Directive, Concessions Directive, Public Procurement Directive, Utilities Procurement Directive, Market Surveillance Directive, Accounting Directive, and Transparency Directive.
2. **Environmental legislation:** 19 items, covering the principal environmental and industrial risk items (EIA, SEA, Environmental Liability, REACH, etc.).
3. **Waste legislation:** 13 items where the Extractive Waste Directive and related Commission Decisions are discussed, among other waste-related items (Waste Framework Directive, Landfill Directive).
4. **Water legislation:** six items, including surface water and groundwater topics.
5. **Nature conservation legislation:** the two major pieces, the Habitats and the Birds Directive.

6. **Noise and atmospheric pollution:** eight items.
7. **Health and safety:** 24 items covering different aspects of occupational health and safety.
8. **Statistics, nomenclature and information management:** seven different items.
9. **Other relevant legislation:** 11 items that are resource-related pieces and cover energy minerals or topics such as underground CO₂ storage. Court case analysis indicated that some cases from the energy minerals sector may be important and relevant to the project if the reason for appeal concerns some general internal market principle.

All these will also be relevant for the permitting stage and the operational supervision of combined extraction projects. Since the Min-Lex-study was completed in 2017, a number of additional EU regulatory instruments, such as the Energy Efficiency Directive 2023/1791 (CEU 2023), have been put into place and various national regulations have been revised.

There is no comparable compendium specifically on national environmental regulatory instruments. In order to better understand the relevance and potential and actual impacts of certain EU Directives and regulations, it is helpful to order these according to the life-cycle of extractive activities, namely exploration, extraction, beneficiation/processing, intermediates, final products, wastes (including those from de-scaling operations and other process wastes), recycling, and long-term management of former combined extraction sites and their potential extractive waste management facilities.

Certain host-rocks of combined extraction systems may contain heavy metals, (toxic) metalloids, and/or Naturally Occurring Radioactive Materials (NORM; see e.g. Eggeling et al., 2013), which may appear in dissolved form in hydrothermal fluids. These elements will likely partition into by-products and/or residues/wastes during processing and then need to be managed adequately (see inter alia the Extractive Waste Directive 2006/21/EC). Relevant OSH aspects, including handling of contaminated equipment are discussed below summarily, see e.g. Directive 2013/59/Euratom (CEU 2013).

Table 1 below provides a non-exhaustive list of Environmental EU legislative acts (Directives / Regulations / Decisions) relevant to the extractive sector and potentially applicable to combined extraction systems. The operational health and safety aspects are discussed in Section 4.2. Links to the respective regulatory acts are given in Appendix 1.

The European Emissions Trading System (EU ETS, https://climate.ec.europa.eu/eu-action/eu-emissions-trading-system-eu-ets_en) is a market-based mechanism that aims to reduce greenhouse gas emissions from industry and power generation. Geothermal energy is considered a low-carbon energy source and is eligible for emission credits under this system. The economic and business case aspects associated with the ETS, however, are discussed in Deliverable D4.3 of this project (Correia et al., forthcoming).

Table 1: Extractive operation life-cycle relevance of EU Directives and Regulations.

Directive / Regulation	No.
Environment	
Strategic Environmental Impact Assessment (SEIA)	2001/42/EC
Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA)	2014/52/EU
Environmental Liability Directive	2004/35/EC
Hazardous Chemicals (CLP Regulation)	1272/2008
Water Framework	2000/60/EC
Groundwater	2006/118/EC
Seveso Directive III	2012/18/EU
IED	2024/1785
Habitat	92/43/EEC
Birds	2009/147/EC
Waste	
Waste Framework (WFD)	2008/98/EC
Extractive Waste (EWD)	2006/21/EC
Hazardous Waste Regulations	1357/2014, 2017/997
List of Waste (LoW) Decision	2014/955/EC
Landfill	1999/31/EC
Human Health	
Restrictions of Hazardous Substances (RoHS)	2011/65/EU
Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH)	1907/2006
Sustainability	
Renewable energy	2009/28/EC
Renewable energies (RES)	2018/2001
Energy efficiency	2023/1791
Eco-design	2009/125/EC
Eco-management audit Regulation	1221/2009
Societal	
Public participation	2003/35/EC

4.2 REGULATIONS ON OCCUPATIONAL SAFETY AND HEALTH (OSH)

Occupational Safety and Health (OSH) is not only relevant for the workers setting up and operating combined extraction facilities, but also for the surrounding communities and thus the social license to operate (Mitchell et al., 2025). The reason is that the workers typically are members of the local communities and the image of the operating company is strongly shaped by its attitude towards OSH and the well-being of its employees.

The EU has developed a comprehensive set of general OSH regulations, but also specific ones for the extractive industries (see Table 2 below). The OSH Framework Directive (CEU, 1989) guarantees minimum safety and health requirements throughout Europe, while MSs may establish stricter requirements. It contains principles relating to the assessment, elimination and prevention of risks and accident factors, the protection of safety and health, the informing, consultation and balanced participation, and training of workers and their representatives.

On the basis of this Framework Directive, some 30 specific Directives were adopted (Table 3; <https://osha.europa.eu/en/safety-and-health-legislation/european-directives>), which are grouped according to the following categories: workplaces, equipment, signs, personal protective equipment; exposure to chemical agents and chemical safety; exposure to physical hazards; exposure to biological agents; provisions on workload, ergonomic and psychosocial risks; sector specific and worker related provisions.

Five of these directives have special importance for the extractive industries, namely 92/91/EEC (CEU, 1992a) setting minimum requirements for improving the safety and health of workers engaged in drilling operations in the extractive industries; 92/104/EEC (CEU, 1992b) establishing minimum OSH requirements in surface and underground mineral-extracting industries; 2003/10/EC on the risks arising from physical agents such as noise (CEU, 2003) and 2002/44/EC on vibration (CEU, 2002) as well as 2004/37/EC on the exposure to carcinogens or mutagens at work (CEU, 2004), which include mineral dusts from e.g. silica and coal, or fibres of certain asbestos minerals.

The main risks that may arise during the various phases of an extractive project or its ancillary operations, will need to be defined and assessed in the Technical Operation Plan (TOP). Definition of health and safety rules are a substantial part of the permitting process. Risk assessment included in the TOPs will need to consider all possible health and safety factors, especially concerning the work equipment used, hazardous substances and mixtures, occupational exposure of workers to different substances, noise, vibration or ionising radiation, as well as the ergonomic set-up of the workplaces.

A number of studies in recent years have summarised (e.g. Falck et al., 2017) and also critically evaluated the regulations (e.g. Min-Lex, 2017), where one can find more detailed information on these instruments.

Table 2: OSH relevant EU Directives

Subject area	Directive No.
Overarching instruments	
Introduction of measures to encourage improvements in the safety and health of workers at work – OSH Framework Directive	89/391/EEC
Minimum safety and health requirements for the workplace	89/654/EEC
Minimum requirements for improving the safety and health protection of workers in <i>surface and underground mineral-extracting industries</i>	92/104/EEC
Minimum requirements for improving the safety and health protection of workers in the mineral- extracting industries through <i>drilling</i>	92/91/EEC
Workplaces, equipment, signs, personal protective equipment	
Minimum safety and health requirements for the use of <i>work equipment</i> by workers at work	2009/104/EC
Minimum health and safety requirements for the use by workers of <i>personal protective equipment</i> at the workplace	89/656/EEC
Minimum requirements for the provision of safety and/or health <i>signs</i> at work	92/58/EEC
Minimum requirements for improving the health and safety protection of workers potentially at risk from <i>explosive atmospheres</i>	1999/92/EC
Workload, ergonomics, and psychosocial risks	
Minimum health and safety requirements for the <i>manual handling of loads</i> where there is a risk particularly of back injury to workers	90/269/EEC
Minimum safety and health requirements at <i>temporary or mobile construction sites</i>	92/57/EEC
Working time concerning certain aspects of the organisation of working time	2003/88/EC
On temporary workers	91/383/EEC
Chemical agents	
Chemical agents and its individual Directives 2000/39, 2006/15, 2009/161, and 2017/164 on lists of indicative occupational exposure limit values	98/24/EC
On the protection of workers from the risks related to exposure to carcinogens, mutagens or reprotoxic substances at work	2004/37/EC
Classification, labelling and packaging of substances and mixtures (CLP) of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2008 on classification, labelling and packaging of substances and mixtures, amending and repealing Directives 67/548/EEC and 1999/45/EC, and amending Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006	Regulation (EC) 1272/2008
Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH) of 18 December 2006 concerning the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH) and establishing a European Chemicals Agency	Regulation (EC) 1907/2006
Biological agents	
On the protection of workers from risks related to exposure to <i>biological agents</i> at work	2000/54/EC
Physical agents	
Minimum health and safety requirements regarding the exposure of workers to the risks arising from physical agents (<i>vibration</i>)	2002/44/EC
Minimum health and safety requirements regarding the exposure of workers to the risks arising from physical agents (<i>noise</i>)	2003/10/EC
Minimum health and safety requirements regarding the exposure of workers to the risks arising from physical agents (<i>electromagnetic fields</i>)	2004/40/EC
Minimum health and safety requirements regarding the exposure of workers to risks arising from physical agents (<i>artificial optical radiation</i>)	2006/25/EC
Radiation protection	2013/59/Euratom

5 SELECTED EUROPEAN STATES' LEGISLATION AND POLICIES

The Icelandic law firm BBA/FJELDCO (<https://www.bbafjeldco.is>) maintains an *Geothermal Transparency Guide* as an online database (<http://www.geothermal.bba.is>), which is intended to provide an insight into the legal frameworks governing exploration, exploitation and production of electricity from geothermal resources. It covers a variety of countries including some EU MSs (Table 3 below).

Table 3: Overview over regulatory coverage in various European countries (from EGECE 2005?)

	Legislative framework							
	Geothermal energy explicitly treated in					Specific legislation on geo-thermal energy	Ownership of in situ geothermal energy	
	mining	water	environmental	energy or electricity	other legislation		state	land-owner
Albania	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes	No
Belgium	No	No	No	No	No	No		
Czech Republic	no	yes	no	yes	no	no	-	-
France	yes	no	no	no	no	yes	yes	no
Germany	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	yes	no
Germany II	yes	no	no	no	yes	no	yes	sometimes
Hungary	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	no	yes	no
Latvia	no	yes	no	yes	no	no	yes	no
Lithuania	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	no	yes	no
Poland								
Romania	yes	yes	no	yes	no	no	yes	no
Serbia and Montenegro	yes	no	no	no	no	no	yes	no
Slovakia	no	yes	no	no	no	no	yes	no
Slovenia	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	no	yes	no
Switzerland	no	yes	no	no	no	no	yes	no

As noted above, the European Commission initiated a study to summarise policy and legal instruments on both, EU and national level (MinLex, MinPol, 2017). The fact-sheets produced by this study provided a good starting point for the following assessment, although they are now nearly ten years old.

The EU Raw Materials Information System (RMIS) maintained by the Joint Research Centre of the European Commission also provides legislative country profiles for the EU Member States: <https://rmis.jrc.ec.europa.eu/member-states-legislation-08b84e>. The data are based on the MinLex (2017) study, but also include the results from the MinGuide project. It is not known, whether the information in RMIS is updated periodically.

As noted earlier, particularly useful was the regulatory and policies database of the Food and Agriculture Organisation of United Nations (<https://www.fao.org/faolex/en/>). It covers all FAO Member States and provides links to either the original legislative/ policy documents or translations (both official and unofficial).

It may be also noted here that ChatGPT (<https://chatgpt.com>), which became fully operational during the course of this project, proved to be a very useful tool to get a first understanding of the regulatory framework of a specific country and to re-review work

undertaken earlier. On the basis of these results, a targeted research for the original legislative documents could be undertaken to provide a solid reference framework.

The regulatory country review focused on the legislation that would be applicable in particular to the extraction of mineral value from deep geothermal waters and not on geothermal energy systems, particularly shallow ones, in general. The respective country profiles are given in Appendix 2.

6 REGULATORY CHALLENGES TO PERMITTING OF COMBINED EXTRACTION PROJECTS

There appear to be three different legal approaches to resource ownership across Europe: a) all resources in the ground belong to the land-owner, b) all resources in the ground belong to the state, c) deep resources belong to the state, while shallow (i.e. down to a few metres of depth) belong to the land-owner. In some European countries there may be also hybrid situations, where resources in the ground in principle belong to the land-owner with the exception of hydrocarbons or precious metals for instance. Given such situations, granting access to the resource and granting access to the land above the resource for the purpose of extraction may involve more than one entity.

Actual permitting processes for specific projects will be governed by the applicable national legislation. As can be seen In Appendix 2, in the majority of European countries, including those the EU MSs, (deep) geothermal projects are controlled by the national mining codes, which in most cases include drilling operations.

In practice, the domain of interest of a range of different regulators may be concerned, including the water (resources) authorities, mining and environmental regulators, regional/spatial planners, etc. *A priori* it may not be clear which one of these might be the leading regulator when it comes to assess the potential environmental impacts. ESGS (2021) recommended the setting up of ‘one-stop shops’ in the MSs to simplify the permitting procedures. However, regulator would need to be competent for both, shallow systems and deep systems with all the implications the latter have. For combined extraction, it would be desirable to have a regulator capable of a systemic assessment, encompassing the resource (conservation), environmental, technological, OHS, economic, and not the least the societal dimension of such projects. Other MSs *de facto* apply the ‘one-stop-shop’ principle by designating one of the regulatory authorities as the lead regulator that collates the processes.

A further challenge arises from the fact that in many EU MSs, due to the lack of mining in recent decades, mining authorities have been either closed for good or have been amalgamated with e.g. environmental authorities. The focus on the environmental aspects of mining has resulted in various cases in an erosion of the technical competence to adequately evaluate and regulate extractive projects, including deep drilling projects. The latter requires an understanding of drilling and casing technologies, as well as reservoir hydraulics, but positions may not have been filled with adequately trained staff.

Given the fact that combined extraction projects might be close to urban centres, particularly, when they deliver heat, rather than electricity, a range of competing use interests for the subsurface space may exist. In general, the footprint of geothermal and

combined extraction systems is small compared to conventional mining operation. Hence, surface use conflicts are less likely to arise.

In summary, it is probably safe to state that in any one given European country the regulatory treatment would depend on what the primary objective of the project is: extraction of heat or extraction of metal value. If the main objective is extraction of heat, in the first instance the regulations pertaining to geothermal energy systems would apply. If the main objective is extraction of metal value, the respective mining legislation would apply and the system may be treated as a solution mining project. While in practical terms this will not change dramatically the investigations necessary for an adequate environmental impact assessment, the main difference would be how resulting residues and wastes are treated from a regulatory point of view. If the project *de jure* is a mining project, the Extractive Waste Directive (CEU 2006a) would apply, otherwise wastes would be treated as industrial wastes under the Waste Framework Directive (CEU 2008b).

7 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

At the time of writing (Summer 2025), the majority of European countries do not have explicit regulations for the combined extraction of heat and mineral value. It is probably safe to state that in any one given European country the regulatory treatment would depend on what the primary objective of the project is: extraction of heat or extraction of metal value. If the main objective is extraction of heat, in the first instance the laws pertaining to geothermal energy systems would apply. If the main objective is extraction of metal value, the respective mining legislation would apply and the system would be treated as a solution mining project. While in practical terms this would not change the investigations necessary for an adequate environmental impact assessment, the main difference would be how resulting residues and wastes are treated from a regulatory point of view.

8 REFERENCES

- ARRIZABALAGA, I. ET AL. (2019): Geothermal Energy Use, Country Update for Spain.- Proc. European Geothermal Congress, Den Haag, The Netherlands, 11-14 June 2019: 9 p., <https://europeangeothermalcongress.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/10/EGC2019.pdf> (accessed 30.09.25).
- BATINI, F. (2021): Proposal for a Harmonized European Geothermal Licensing Guidelines.- Report for the H2020 GEOENVIE Project: 7 p., https://www.geoenvi.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/European-Geothermal-Licensing-guidelines_FINAL-DRAFT_HE31052021.pdf (accessed 30.09.25).
- CRMA EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND COUNCIL (2024): Regulation (EU) 2024/1252 of 11 April 2024 establishing a framework for ensuring a secure and sustainable supply of critical raw materials and amending Regulations (EU) No 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, (EU) 2018/1724 and (EU) 2019/1020.- OJ L Series, 03.05.24, 67 p., https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=OJ:L_202401252.
- DUMAS, P., SERDJUK, M., KUTSCHICK, R., FRASER, S., REITH, S., KOELBEL, T. (2013): Report presenting proposals for improving the regulatory framework for geothermal electricity.- Deliverable 4.1 – Annex 1: Overview of national regulations for geothermal electricity, Project GEOELEC, 40 p., <http://www.geoelec.eu/wp-content/uploads/2011/09/4.1.pdf>, <http://www.geoelec.eu/wp-content/uploads/2011/09/D4.1-A.1-Overview-of-National-Rules-of-Licensing.pdf> (accessed 30.09.25).
- EGEC – EUROPEAN GEOTHERMAL ENERGY COUNCIL (2005?): K4RES-H - Key Issue 3 : Regulations for Geothermal Energy.- Report K4RES-H Project: 37 p., http://geodh.eu/wp-content/uploads/2012/11/K4RES-H_Geothermal_Regulations.pdf (accessed 30.09.25).
- EGEC – EUROPEAN GEOTHERMAL ENERGY COUNCIL (2022): Guidance on Licensing and Permitting – Case Geothermal Energy.- 40 p., <https://www.egec.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/08/Guidance-on-licensing-and-permitting-of-geothermal-projects-EGEC.pdf> (accessed 30.09.25).
- FRENZ, W. (2020): The Current Legal Framework for Geothermal Drilling – Geothermiebohrungen im aktuellen rechtlichen Kontext.- Mining Report Glückauf, 156(6): 567-577, https://mining-report.de/wp-content/uploads/pda/2020/12/MRG_2006_Rechtlicher_Kontext_Geothermie_Frenz_201204.pdf (accessed 30.09.25).
- GOODMAN, R., ET AL. (2009): Geothermal Regulation Framework.- Final report from the Geothermal Regulation-Heat (GTR-H) project: no pagination, http://www.geoelec.eu/wp-content/uploads/2012/11/GTRH_final_Framework_Nov09.pdf (accessed 30.09.25).
- HANNONEN, K. (2020): Regulatory Framework on Geothermal Energy in Finland - Lessons learned from the Deep Heat-project in Otaniemi, Espoo.- Thesis, Itä-Suomen Yliopisto Environment and Climate Change Law: 55 p., https://erepo.uef.fi/bitstream/handle/123456789/22939/urn_nbn_fi_uef-20200855.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y (accessed 30.09.25).
- IEA INTERNATIONAL ENERGY AGENCY (2021): Spain 2021 – Energy Policy Review.- 242 p., <https://iea.blob.core.windows.net/assets/2f405ae0-4617-4e16-884c-7956d1945f64/Spain2021.pdf> (accessed 24.09.25).

- LAGROU, D., PETITCLERC, E., HOES, H., DUPONT, N., LAENEN, B. (2019): Geothermal Energy Use, Country Update for Belgium.- European Geothermal Congress 2019, Den Haag, The Netherlands, 11-14 June 2019: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/335466240_Geothermal_Energy_Use_Country_Update_for_Belgium#fullTextFileContent (accessed 30.09.25).
- MINLEX - MINPOL GMBH ET AL. (2017): Study - Legal framework for mineral extraction and permitting procedures for exploration and exploitation in the EU.- Report to the European Commission, DG GROW: 1920 p., <https://doi.org/10.2873/920344>.
- SZALEWSKA, M. (2021): Legal Aspects of Geothermal Energy Use in Poland.- Comparative Law Review, **27**: 385-406, <https://doi.org/10.12775/CLR.2021.017>.
- TZEFERIS, P.G. (2018): The Licensing System for Mines and Quarrying Works in Greece, 2018.- 7 p., <http://www.latomet.gr/ypan/Hypertrak/BinaryContent.aspx?pagenb=18560> (accessed 30.09.25).
- VALKERING, P. ET AL. (2020): Decision-Making Process Mapping.- H2020 Project GEOENVIE, Deliverable D.4.1: 240 p., <https://www.geoenvi.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/D4.1-Decision-making-process-mapping.pdf> (accessed 30.09.25).

APPENDIX 1 - REFERENCES TO EU REGULATIONS

- CEU Council of the European Union (1967): Council Directive 67/548/EEC of 27 June 1967 on the approximation of laws, regulations and administrative provisions relating to the classification, packaging and labelling of dangerous substances.- OJ No. 196/1, p. 234-256, 16.08.1967, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:31967L0548&from=EN>.
- CEU Council of the European Union (1985): Council Directive 85/337/EEC of 27 June 1985 on the assessment of the effects of certain public and private projects on the environment.- OJ L 175/40-48, 5.7.1985, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:31985L0337&from=EN>.
- CEU Council of the European Union (1989): Council Directive 89/391/EEC of 12 June 1989 on the introduction of measures to encourage improvements in the safety and health of workers at work.- OJ 183/1-183/8 of 26.06.89, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:31989L0391&from=EN>.
- CEU Council of the European Union (1991): Council Directive 91/689/EEC of 12 December 1991 on hazardous waste.- OJ L377/20-27, 31.12.1991, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:31991L0689&from=EN>.
- CEU Council of the European Union (1992): Directive 92/43/EEC on the conservation of natural habitats and of wild fauna and flora (Habitats Directive).- OJ L206/7-50, 22.7.92, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:31992L0043&from=EN>.
- CEU Council of the European Union (1992): Council Directive 92/57/EEC of 24 June 1992 on the implementation of minimum safety and health requirements at temporary or mobile construction sites (eighth individual Directive within the meaning of Article 16 (1) of Directive 89/391/EEC).- OJ L 245/6-22, 26.8.1992, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:01992L0057-20190726&from=EN>.
- CEU Council of the European Union (1992): Council Directive 92/91/EEC of 3 November 1992 concerning the minimum requirements for improving the safety and health protection of workers in the mineral-extracting industries through drilling (eleventh individual Directive within the meaning of Article 16 (1) of Directive 89/391/EEC).- OJ L348/9-24, 28.11.92, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:31992L0091&from=EN>.
- CEU Council of the European Union (1992): Council Directive 92/104/EEC of 3 December 1992 on the minimum requirements for improving the safety and health protection of workers in surface and underground mineral-extracting industries (twelfth individual Directive within the meaning of Article 16 (1) of Directive 89/391/EEC).- OJ L 404/10-25, 31.12.1992, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:31992L0104&from=EN>.
- CEU Council of the European Union (1996): Council Directive 96/61/EC of 24 September 1996 concerning integrated pollution prevention and control.- OJ L 257/26-40, 10.10.1996, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:31996L0061&from=EN>.

- CEU Council of the European Union (1996): Council Directive 96/82/EC of 9 December 1996 on the control of major-accident hazards involving dangerous substances (Seveso Directive).- OJ L 10/13-33, 14.01.97, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:31996L0082&from=EN>.
- CEU Council of the European Union (1997): Council Directive 97/11/EC of 3 March 1997 amending Directive 85/337/EEC on the assessment of the effects of certain public and private projects on the environment.- OJ L 073/5-15, 14.03.1997, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:31997L0011&from=EN>.
- CEU Council of the European Union (1999): Council Directive 1999/31/EC of 26 April 1999 on the landfill of waste.- OJ L 182/1-19, 16.7.1999, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:31999L0031&from=EN>.
- CEU Council of the European Union (1999): Directive 1999/45/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 31 May 1999 concerning the approximation of the laws, regulations and administrative provisions of the Member States relating to the classification, packaging and labelling of dangerous preparations.- OJ L200/1-68, 30.07.1999, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:31999L0045&from=en>.
- CEU Council of the European Union (1999): Council Directive 1999/92/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 1999 on minimum requirements for improving the safety and health protection of workers potentially at risk from explosive atmospheres (15th individual Directive within the meaning of Article 16(1) of Directive 89/391/EEC.- 8 p., <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legalcontent/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:31999L0092&from=EN>.
- CEU Council of the European Union (2000): Directive 2000/60/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 October 2000 establishing a framework for Community action in the field of water policy (Water Framework Directive).- OJ L 327/1-73, 22.12.2000, https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:5c835afb-2ec6-4577-bdf8-756d3d694eeb.0004.02/DOC_1&format=PDF.
- CEU Council of the European Union (2001): Directive 2001/42/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 June 2001 on the assessment of the effects of certain plans and programmes on the environment.- OJ L 197/30-37, 21.7.2001, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32001L0042&from=EN>.
- CEU Council of the European Union (2001): Regulation (EC) No 761/2001 of the European parliament and of the council of 19 March 2001 allowing voluntary participation by organisations in a Community eco-management and audit scheme (EMAS).- OJ L 114/1-29, 24.04.01, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2001:114:0001:0029:EN:PDF>.
- CEU Council of the European Union (2002): Directive 2002/44/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 June 2002 on the minimum health and safety requirements regarding the exposure of workers to the risks arising from physical agents (vibration) (sixteenth individual Directive within the meaning of Article 16(1) of Directive 89/391/EEC) - Joint Statement by the European Parliament and the Council.- OJ L 177/13-20, 6.7.2002, https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:546a09c0-3ad1-4c07-bcd5-9c3dae6b1668.0004.02/DOC_1&format=PDF.

- CEU Council of the European Union (2003): Directive 2003/35/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 May 2003 providing for public participation in respect of the drawing up of certain plans and programmes relating to the environment and amending with regard to public participation and access to justice Council Directives 85/337/EEC and 96/61/EC - Statement by the Commission.- OJ L 156/17-25, 25.06.2003. https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:4a80a6c9-cdb3-4e27-a721-d5df1a0535bc.0004.02/DOC_1&format=PDF.
- CEU Council of the European Union (2003): Directive 2003/10/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 6 February 2003 on the minimum health and safety requirements regarding the exposure of workers to the risks arising from physical agents (noise) (Seventeenth individual Directive within the meaning of Article 16(1) of Directive 89/391/EEC).- OJ L 42/38-44, 15.2.2003, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32003L0010&from=en>.
- CEU Council of Europe (2003): Directive 2002/95/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 January 2003 on the restriction of the use of certain hazardous substances in electrical and electronic equipment.- OJ L 37/19-23, 13.2.2003, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32002L0095&from=EN>.
- CEU Council of the European Union (2003): Directive 2003/105/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2003 amending Council Directive 96/82/EC on the control of major-accident hazards involving dangerous substances.- OJ L 345/97-105, 31.12.2003, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32003L0105&from=EN>.
- CEU Council of the European Union (2004): Directive 2004/35/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 April 2004 on environmental liability with regard to the prevention and remedying of environmental damage (Environmental Liability Directive).- OJ L 143/56-75, 30.04.04. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legalcontent/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32004L0035&from=EN>
- CEU Council of the European Union (2004): Directive 2004/37/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 29 April 2004 on the protection of workers from the risks related to exposure to carcinogens, mutagens or reprotoxic substances at work (Sixth individual Directive within the meaning of Article 16(1) of Council Directive 89/391/EEC) (codified version).- OJ L 158/50-76, 30.4.2004, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:02004L0037-20220405&from=EN>.
- CEU Council of the European Union (2006a): Directive 2006/21/EC of 15 March 2006 on the management of waste from extractive industries and amending Directive 2004/35/EC.- OJ L 102/15-33, 11.04.2006, https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:c370006a-063e-4dc7-9b05-52c37720740c.0005.02/DOC_1&format=PDF.
- CEU Council of the European Union (2006b): Directive 2006/42/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 May 2006 on machinery, and amending Directive 95/16/EC (recast).- OJ L 157/24-86, 6.9.2006, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32006L0042&from=EN>.
- CEU Council of the European Union (2006c): Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 December 2006 concerning the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH).- OJ L

396/1-520, 30.12.2006, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:02006R1907-20140410&from=EN>.

CEU Council of the European Union (2006d): Directive 2006/118/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 December 2006 on the protection of groundwater against pollution and deterioration.- OJ L 372/19-31, 27.12.2006, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32006L0118>.

CEU Council of the European Union (2008a): Directive 2008/1/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 January 2008 concerning integrated pollution prevention and control (Codified version).- OJ L24/8-29, 29.01.2008. <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2008:024:0008:0029:en:PDF>.

CEU Council of the European Union (2008b): Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 November 2008 on waste and repealing certain Directives (Waste Framework Directive).- OJ L 312/3-30, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32008L0098&from=EN>.

CEU Council of the European Union (2008): Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2008 on classification, labelling and packaging of substances and mixtures, amending and repealing Directives 67/548/EEC and 1999/45/EC, and amending Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006.- OJ L 353/1-1355, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2008:353:0001:1355:en:PDF>.

CEU Council of the European Union (2009): Directive 2009/28/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 April 2009 on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources and amending and subsequently repealing Directives 2001/77/EC and 2003/30/EC.- OJ L140/16-62, 5.6.2009, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32009L0028&from=EN>.

CEU Council of the European Union (2009): Directive 2009/104/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 September 2009 concerning the minimum safety and health requirements for the use of work equipment by workers at work (second individual Directive within the meaning of Article 16(1) of Directive 89/391/EEC).- OJ 260/5-19, 3.10.2009, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32009L0104&from=EN>.

CEU Council of the European Union (2009): Directive 2009/147/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 November 2009 on the conservation of wild birds.- OJ L 20/7-25, 26.1.2010, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32009L0147&from=EN>.

CEU Council of the European Union (2009): Regulation (EC) No 1221/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 November 2009 on the voluntary participation by organisations in a Community eco-management and audit scheme (EMAS), repealing Regulation (EC) No 761/2001 and Commission Decisions 2001/681/EC and 2006/193/EC.- OJ L 342/1-45, 22.12.2009, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32009R1221&from=en>.

CEU Council of the European Union (2010): Directive 2010/75/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 November 2010 on industrial emissions (Integrated Pollution Prevention and Control) (Recast).- OJ L 334/17-119, 17.12.2010, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32010L0075&from=EN>.

- CEU Council of the European Union (2012a): Directive 2012/18/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 4 July 2012 on the control of major-accident hazards involving dangerous substances, amending and subsequently repealing Council Directive 96/82/EC (Seveso III Directive).- OJ 197/1-L197/37, 24.07.2012, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32012L0018&from=HR>.
- CEU Council of the European Union (2012b): Directive 2012/19/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 4 July 2012 on waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE) - (recast).- OJ L197/38-71, 24.07.2012, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2012:197:0038:0071:EN:PDF>.
- CEU Council of Europe (2012c): Directive 2012/19/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 4 July 2012 on waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE).- OJ L 197/38-71, 24.7.2012, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32012L0019&from=EN>.
- CEU Council of Europe (2013): Council Directive 2013/59/Euratom of 5 December 2013 laying down basic safety standards for protection against the dangers arising from exposure to ionising radiation, and repealing Directives 89/618/Euratom, 90/641/Euratom, 96/29/Euratom, 97/43/Euratom and 2003/122/Euratom.- OJ L 13/1-73, 17.1.2014, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32013L0059&from=EN>.
- CEU Council of Europe (2014a): Directive 2014/52/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 April 2014 amending Directive 2011/92/EU on the assessment of the effects of certain public and private projects on the environment (Environmental Impact Assessment Directive).- OJ 124/1-18, 25.4.2014, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32014L0052>.
- CEU Council of Europe (2014b): Directive 2014/52/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 October 2014 amending Directive 2013/34/EU as regards disclosure of non-financial and diversity information by certain large undertakings and groups.- OJ L330/1-9, 15.11.24, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32014L0095>.
- CEU Council of Europe (2017): Council Regulation (EU) 2017/997 of 8 June 2017 amending Annex III to Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council as regards the hazardous property HP 14 'Ecotoxic'.- OJ L150/1-4, 14.6.2017, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32017R0997&from=EN>.
- CEU Council of Europe (2018): Directive (EU) 2018/2001 of The European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2018 on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources.- OJ L 328/82-209, 21.12.2018, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32018L2001&from=EN>.
- CEU Council of Europe (2019): Regulation (EU) 2019/1239 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 establishing a European Maritime Single Window environment and repealing Directive 2010/65/EU.- OJ L 198/64-87, 25.7.2019, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:32019R1239>.
- CEU Council of Europe (2023): Directive (EU) 2023/1791 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 September 2023 on energy efficiency and amending Regulation (EU) 2023/955 (recast) (Text with EEA relevance) PE/15/2023/INIT.- OJ L 231/1-111, 20.9.2023, https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ%3AJOL_2023_231_R_0001&qid=1695186598766.

- CEU Council of Europe (2024): Directive (EU) 2024/1785 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 April 2024 amending Directive 2010/75/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council on industrial emissions (integrated pollution prevention and control) and Council Directive 1999/31/EC on the landfill of waste.- OJ L, 15.07.2024, https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=OJ:L_202401785.
- European Commission (2001): Implementation of Directive 2001/42 on the Assessment of the Effects of certain Plans and Programmes on the Environment.- http://ec.europa.eu/environment/archives/eia/pdf/030923_sea_guidance.pdf
- European Commission (2006): Clarification of the Application of Article 2(3) of the EIA Directive.- ISBN 92-79-01036-0, 11 p., Luxembourg, http://ec.europa.eu/environment/archives/eia/pdf/eia_art2_3.pdf
- European Commission (2009): Commission Decision 2009/335/EC of 20 April 2009 on technical guidelines for the establishment of the financial guarantee in accordance with Directive 2006/21/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council concerning the management of waste from extractive industries (notified under document number C(2009) 2798).- OJ L 102/25, 21.04.09, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2009:101:0025:0025:EN:PDF>
- European Commission (2009): Commission Decision 2009/337/EC of 20 April 2009 on the definition of the criteria for the classification of waste facilities in accordance with Annex III of Directive 2006/21/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council concerning the management of waste from extractive industries (notified under document number C(2009) 2856).- OJ L 102/7-11, 22.04.09, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2009:102:0007:0011:EN:PDF>
- European Commission (2009): Commission Decision 2009/358/EC: of 29 April 2009 on the harmonisation, the regular transmission of the information and the questionnaire referred to in Articles 22(1)(a) and 18 of Directive 2006/21/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council on the management of waste from extractive industries (notified under document number C(2009) 3011).- OJ L 110/39-45, 01.05.09, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2009:110:0039:0045:EN:PDF>
- European Commission (2009): Commission Decision 2009/359/EC of 30 April 2009 completing the definition of inert waste in implementation of Article 22(1)(f) of Directive 2006/21/EC of the European Parliament and the Council concerning the management of waste from extractive industries (notified under document number C(2009) 3012).- OJ L 110/46-47, 01.05.2009, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2009:110:0046:0047:EN:PDF>
- European Commission (2009): Commission Decision 2009/360/EC of 30 April 2009 completing the technical requirements for waste characterisation laid down by Directive 2006/21/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council on the management of waste from extractive industries (notified under document number C(2009) 3013).- OJ L 110/48-51, 1.5.2009, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2009:110:0048:0051:EN:PDF>.
- European Commission (2014a): Commission Regulation (EU) No 1357/2014 of 18 December 2014 replacing Annex III to Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council on waste and repealing certain Directives.- OJ L365/89-96, 19.12.2014, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32014R1357&from=EN>.

- European Commission (2014b): Commission Decision 2014/955/EU of 18 December 2014 amending Decision 2000/532/EC on the list of waste pursuant to Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council.- OJ 370/44-86, 30.12.2014, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32014D0955&from=EN>.
- European Commission (2019): Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions: The European Green Deal.- COM(2019) 640 final of 11.12.2019: 24 p., https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:b828d165-1c22-11ea-8c1f-01aa75ed71a1.0002.02/DOC_1&format=PDF.
- European Commission (2023): Commission Delegated Regulation (Eu) 2023/2772 of 31 July 2023 supplementing Directive 2013/34/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council as regards sustainability reporting standards.- OJ L 2772/1-335, 22.12.2023, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:02023R2772-20231222>.
- European Parliament and Council of the Europe Union (2006): Directive 2006/21/EC of 15 March 2006 on the management of waste from extractive industries and amending Directive 2004/35/EC.- OJ L 102/15-33, 11.04.2006, https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:c370006a-063e-4dc7-9b05-52c37720740c.0005.02/DOC_1&format=PDF.
- EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND COUNCIL (2024): Regulation (EU) 2024/1252 of 11 April 2024 establishing a framework for ensuring a secure and sustainable supply of critical raw materials and amending Regulations (EU) No 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, (EU) 2018/1724 and (EU) 2019/1020.- OJ L Series, 03.05.24, 67 p., https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=OJ:L_202401252

APPENDIX 2 – COUNTRY REGULATORY SYSTEMS FOR COMBINED EXTRACTION

While most of the review work was undertaken in 2023, the work was revisited in June 2025 in order to assure that recent regulatory and policy developments are captured that may be relevant for combined extraction projects.

8.1 AUSTRIA

Geothermal exploration and exploitation are governed by a range of laws and regulations at both, the federal and regional level. At the federal level, the main laws and regulations that apply include the Federal Mining Act (Bundesberggesetz), the Federal Environmental Impact Assessment Act (UVP-G), and the Federal Waste Management Act (AWG). The Geothermal Energy Act (Geothermiegesetz) sets out the legal framework for the exploration, exploitation, and use of geothermal energy. It defines the conditions and procedures for obtaining permits and licenses for geothermal activities, as well as the environmental and safety standards that must be met.

Metal ores in general are 'free to mine' ('bergfrei'), but require a mining license by the government (MinLex 2017). The same applies to geothermal resources, which also belong to the land-owner (<https://www.360ee.at/energie-aus-der-tiefe-rechtliche-grundlagen-der-geothermie/>).

Drill-holes below 300 m depth require a license under the mineral resources act (MinroG) by the competent mining regulator. If water is to be extracted, this requires a license under the water resources act (WRG 1959), which also regulates the re-injection. If the amount extracted exceed 10^6 m³ annually, an environmental impact assessment is required per UVP-G.

The Renewable Energy Act (Erneuerbaren-Ausbau-Gesetz) promotes the development of renewable energy sources, including geothermal energy. It establishes the framework for feed-in tariffs, incentives, and subsidies for renewable energy projects, as well as the targets and objectives for the development of renewable energy in Austria.

Commercial use for the extraction of heat requires a license under the trade regulations (Gewerbeordnung 1994), if electricity is to be generated, the licenses are issued under the electricity trade and organisation act (Elektrizitätswirtschafts- und organisationsgesetz 2010, EIWOG). Combined heat and electricity projects are treated under the EIWOG 2010. In such licensing procedures also the necessary water resources licenses are issued.

It thus conceivable that this provides also a simple framework for the combined extraction of heat and metals.

At the regional level, each of Austria's nine states has its own laws and regulations governing geothermal exploration and production. These laws may impose additional requirements and standards for geothermal projects, such as zoning and land use regulations, and may also require consultation with local communities and stakeholders. While policy developments over the past couple of years signal a shift toward de-risking and promoting deep geothermal energy harvesting (<https://www.bmf.gv.at/themen/klimapolitik/tiefen-geothermie.html>), the June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

8.2 BELGIUM

Belgium is a Federal State composed of three Regions (Flanders, Wallonia, and Brussels). Following a constitutional reform in 1980 that increasingly divulges federal competencies to the regions, in 2013 the Federal Mining Law was suspended and the competencies for environment, energy and economy (including natural resources) came under regional jurisdiction. While there are different governing laws on permitting and extraction for Flanders and Wallonia, metal ores on the continental shelf are owned by the state and exploration and exploitation requires licenses (MinLex 2017). Deep geothermal systems fall mainly into the competences of the Regions.

In **Flanders** the ‘Decree on deep subsurface’ of 2009 and its implementation regulation of 2011 (<https://navigator.emis.vito.be/detail?wold=40324>) explicitly concern also the exploitation of geothermal energy. Flanders also has implemented in 2018 an insurance system against geological risks (Lagrou et al., 2019). Deep geothermal projects hence need an exploration/exploitation permit according to this Decree, as well as a (Flemish) environmental permit according to the ‘Decree on the environmental permit’ of 2014 (<https://navigator.emis.vito.be/detail?wold=63105>). Shallow geothermal projects only need an environmental permit. Geothermal projects (shallow and deep) in Flanders do not require any permit at federal level.

Currently, there is no law to claim a concession for exploring/exploiting ore deposits or (metallic) mineralisations. No such projects exist in Flanders at the moment, but in case there would, they would fall under regional competence (i.c. natural resources). In practice, at this moment only an environmental permit would be needed for such projects (as is the case for quarries or clay and sand pits).

For metal extraction from geothermal brines, it appears (pers. comm) that regulators currently take the approach that they are inevitable ‘by-products’ from the exploitation of geothermal energy (Decree on the Deep Subsurface, article 63/8 §1), i.e. they fall under the exploration/exploitation license for geothermal projects. If in the future projects would be developed with a main focus on metal extraction from the brine a new regulation would be needed.

In **Wallonia** the legal framework evolves in the same direction, with a new project decree for underground resources management and a similar insurance system (Valkering et al. 2020). The Décret relatif à la gestion des ressources du sous-sol (<https://environnement.wallonie.be/legis/Codeenvironnement/codesoussoledecret.html>) has been adopted on 14 March 2024 and specifically includes deep geothermal resources (Section 4), but does not consider explicitly combined extraction. According to the Website of government of Wallonia, the processes for the application of the new mining legislation is still under revision (<https://www.wallonie.be/en/demarches/applying-grant-transfer-merger-rent-or-lease-mining-concessions#endetail>). It is interesting to note that ‘fracking’ is prohibited in the case of hydrocarbon exploitation, but explicitly permitted for deep geothermal systems.

However, for such projects also a Permis d’environnement according to the decree of 11 March 1999 (https://environnement.wallonie.be/legis/pe/PE001.htm?gad_source=1&gbraid=0AAAAA-BK1fbAuBWJw4J6mX76N_eYnmEdl&gclid=CjwKCAjwvr--BhB5EiwAd5YbXg9wuUbWsfyLLJ9NwT77z1IVEueEfyZ5TPrfUDPai3ULBFbPYLBVcxoCngQAvD_BwE) will

be required. Further, if the produced waters are to be reinjected, a Water Use and Discharge Permit under the federal Code de l'eau of 12 February 2009 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/bel227524.pdf>) will be required.

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

8.3 BULGARIA

All underground ore resources are state owned and exploration and exploitation requires licenses. Mining in Bulgaria is regulated by the Concessions Act (SG No. /36/2.05.2006, <https://www.me.government.bg/en/files/download?hash=e357b9ee3f401efbee64d6a3995ac311a49da805>) and the Subsurface Resources Act (No. 23/12.03.1999, <https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/bul155639.pdf>). However, this Act explicitly does not apply to geothermal waters and the energy contained therein. The Law on Renewable Energy of 2011 (<https://lex.bg/laws/ldoc/2135728864>) has been last amended 18 February 2025 and now mentions geothermal resources.

Other laws of relevance for permitting procedures include the Waste Management Act (53/13.07.2012); the Environmental Protection Act, the Nature Protection Act; the Protected Areas Act (133/11.11.1998); the Act for the protection of the environment (SG 91/25.09.2002, <https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/bul52883.pdf>); the Water Act (67/27.07.1999, <https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/bul33607.pdf>), which also concerns groundwater in geothermal activities, as well as the requirements for monitoring and reporting of groundwater usage; the Law on Biological Diversity (SG/77/09.08.2002, <https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/bul154432.pdf>); and the Protected Areas Act (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/bul67271.pdf>) among others. Bulgaria has a centralised regime where all licenses for all kind of commodities are processed after a written application to the Ministry of Energy (<https://www.me.government.bg/en>). Other relevant co-authorities are the Ministry of Environment and Waters (<https://www.moew.government.bg>) and the Regional Inspectorates on Environment and Water, which coordinate the environmental permitting with the Ministry of Environment. Permits for exploration are granted by the Ministry of Energy upon approval by the Council of Ministers or for the continental shelf and the EEZ by the Council of Ministers (MinLex 2017).

Bulgaria appears to have considerable geothermal potential: <https://www.bage.bg/geothermal-bulgaria>.

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

8.4 CROATIA

All underground ore resources are state owned and exploration and exploitation requires licenses. Croatia has a centralised permitting regime (MinLex 2017).

According to Orkustofnun & EIHP (2017), geothermal waters belong to the mining or mineral resources of the Republic of Croatia and are described in the Mining Act (OG NN 56/13, 14/14, <https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/cro138122.pdf>) as “geothermal waters” that can be used for the accumulation of heat for energy purposes. Geothermal waters that are used for medical, biological and recreational purposes are regulated by the Water Act (OG 153/09, 130/11, 56/13, 14/14, <https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/cro216398.pdf>).

Croatia has a centralised permitting regime and the authorities involved include the Ministry of Economy (issues permits/licenses for exploration and extraction, <http://www.javnabava.hr/>), the Ministry of Environmental and Nature Protection (determines specific conditions, restrictions and consent, impact assessment, <https://mingor.gov.hr/>), the Ministry of Construction and Physical Planning (spatial planning documents necessary to start the procedure for granting a concession, <https://mpgi.gov.hr/>), the Ministry of Finance (provides financial and legal documents necessary to start the procedure for granting a concession, <https://mfin.gov.hr/>) and the Ministry of Agriculture (determines specific conditions relating to exploration and exploitation of mineral resources in forests, water management and agricultural land, <https://poljoprivreda.gov.hr/>).

For the exploitation of mineral resources, a concession is needed for the economic use of a common good according to the Act on Concessions. Concessions for exploitation are given on the basis of a public procurement using a bidding procedure.

Orkustofnun & EIHP (2017) detail the procedure for obtaining an exploitation license and this includes an Environmental Impact Study (EIS). According to the Environmental Protection Act (OG 80/13, 153/13, 78/15, <https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/cro170097.pdf>), before submitting a Request for Determining Environmental Impact a Request for giving instructions on the content of an environmental impact study is made. An EIS is an integral part of a Request for Determining Environmental Impact.

In 2025 amendments to the Renewable Energy Sources Act (RESA, https://narodne-novine.nn.hr/clanci/sluzbeni/2025_05_78_1017.html), along with updates to the Water Act, Underground Resources Act, and Spatial Planning Act, were enacted. Deep geothermal was newly defined as a mineral resource, now regulated under the Underground Resources Act. Permitting was unified: one single authority (Minister of Energy) issues permits for geothermal, replacing dual regimes.

8.5 CYPRUS

Cyprus is one of the EU countries with the longest metal mining history, going back to before the Bronze Age, but there is very little metal mining today.

Cyprus can be considered as a poor country regarding the availability of geothermal resources, since it is located in an inactive tectonic area with no high- or low- enthalpy resources (<http://europeangeothermalcongress.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/07/CUR-07-Cyprus.pdf>).

All underground ore resources are state owned and exploration and exploitation requires licenses and a centralised permitting regime is in place (MinLex 2017).

The legislative framework for the mineral sector in Cyprus is provided by the Mines and Quarries Law of 1965 as amended in 1995, 2001, and 2003 ([https://www.moa.gov.cy/moa/mines/minesSrv.nsf/All/CF7BCA66EE5FDBCDC22574B90035C157/\\$file/Mines%20and%20Quarries%20\(Regulation\)%20Law.pdf](https://www.moa.gov.cy/moa/mines/minesSrv.nsf/All/CF7BCA66EE5FDBCDC22574B90035C157/$file/Mines%20and%20Quarries%20(Regulation)%20Law.pdf)). The Mines Service is the competent authority of the administration of the Mines and Quarries Law and Regulation and the Explosive Substances Law and Regulation ([https://www.moa.gov.cy/moa/mines/minesSrv.nsf/All/C41AB897D6FD4079C22574B20039F5FE/\\$file/Annual%20Report%202018.pdf](https://www.moa.gov.cy/moa/mines/minesSrv.nsf/All/C41AB897D6FD4079C22574B20039F5FE/$file/Annual%20Report%202018.pdf)).

A Town-planning Permit by the Department of Town Planning and Housing is a pre-required document to apply for a Mining Lease or a Quarry Licence

(https://www.moi.gov.cy/moi/tph/tph.nsf/home_en/home_en?openform#). Likewise an Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) study is required according to national law of 2005 on Environmental Impact Assessment from Certain Plans and/or Programmes Law 102(I)/2005 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/cyp87147.pdf>), which seems to mirror the respective EU Directive 2001/42/EC (CEU, 2001).

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

8.6 CZECHIA

All underground ore resources are state owned and exploration and exploitation requires licenses. Mining legislation in the Czech Republic distinguishes between “reserved” minerals, which are state-owned, and “non-reserved” minerals (or deposits) which are owned by the landowner. All minerals, with the exception of building stone, gravel, and clays are “reserved” minerals.

The primary legal basis of mineral extraction activity is the Mining Law (Mining Act) No. 44 of 1988, as amended by Law No. 186 of 2006 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/cze126493.pdf>). For prospecting and exploration for reserved mineral deposits the most relevant law is the one No. 62/1988 Coll., on Geological Work (the Geological Act) as amended. Other important national Acts are the Act on the Environment (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/cze4757.pdf>), the Water Act (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/cze124878.pdf>), the EIA Act (https://www.mzp.cz/en/environmental_impact_assessment). In the field of exploration of mineral deposits, the Ministry of Environment is the most important authority, i.e. the Ministry lays down the exploration areas. In the sphere of exploitation, the District Mining Authorities are the most important state bodies. The District Mining Authorities (eight in total) are part of the State Mining Administration (SMA), which is composed also by the Czech Mining Office in Prague (central mining authority), establishing a centralised permitting regime.

The Energy Act (<https://www.fao.org/faolex/results/details/en/c/LEX-FAOC067101>) also discussed geothermal energy sources. The government commissioned a study on the geothermal potential that was completed in 2022 (<https://www.mpo.cz/en/energy/research-and-development-in-energy-sector/ongoing-completed-projects-and-their-results/analysis-of-the-geothermal-energy-potential-at-medium-and-large-depths-in-the-czech-republic-on-the-basis-of-available-data--260656/>, https://mapy.geology.cz/geotermalni_potencial/#). The ownership and use of deep geothermal resources appeared to be unregulated as of 2014 (Dumas et al. 2013), but it is not clear, whether this still is the case.

With respect to exploitation, the District Mining Authorities are the most important state bodies. The eight Authorities are part of the State Mining Administration (SMA), which includes also by Czech Mining Office in Prague, thus establishing a centralised permitting regime. (MinLex 2017).

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

8.7 DENMARK

All land-based mineral resources belong to the landowner, while off-shore resources belong to the state (MinLex 2017).

The production of geothermal energy is governed by the Subsoil Act and a licence is required for both the exploration for and production of geothermal energy. Licences are provided through a tender by the Danish Environment Agency (DEA). Licences are usually awarded as a sole concession for the applied-for area. Exploration licences last for six years but can be extended for 10 years. Production licenses have a duration of 30 years, but will be limited to the area from which the geothermal energy is actually extracted and will not cover the entire area for which originally an exploration license was initially applied (<https://www.thinkgeoenergy.com/denmark-and-geothermal-district-heating-legal-framework-risk-and-current-development/>).

This seems to imply that it is the landowner's decision to permit the extraction of metal from geothermal energy systems.

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above, however, policy decisions led to a more favourable investment climate in deep systems.

8.8 ESTONIA

All underground ore resources are state owned and exploration and exploitation requires licenses under the Mining Act of 2003 (MinLex 2017). The main responsible authority for mining permitting is the Ministry of Environment (for mineral deposit of national importance), otherwise it is the Environmental Board.

The primary legal basis of mineral extraction activities is the Earth's Crust Act (<https://www.riigiteataja.ee/en/eli/507012019007/consolide>). The main responsible authority for mining permitting is Environmental Board (<https://keskkonnaamet.ee/>). The Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communications (<https://www.mkm.ee/>) is advised (in a non-binding way) by the Commission of Mineral Resources on issues of exploration and exploitation of mineral resources, validation of mineral reserves, among other topics. Supervision and monitoring are conducted by the Environmental Inspectorate (under the Ministry of Climate, <https://kliimaministeerium.ee/>). According to the Earth's Crust Act, holders of an exploration or extraction permit have to ensure that the plans for mining are prepared and the mining operations are conducted under the conditions set by the exploration or extraction permit.

The Water Act (https://www.riigiteataja.ee/en/compare_original/506072023011) permits the discharge of used geothermal waters back into the geological body from which it was taken, but this presumably concerns only shallow systems.

According to the Estonian Geothermal Association (EGA, <http://geothermal.org.ee/eng/>) to date very limited work on deeper resources has been undertaken and no information on the legal basis for exploration and exploitation has been found.

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

8.9 FINLAND

All ores are under the jurisdiction of the state, but royalties go to the landowners (MinLex 2017).

Currently there is no legislation in force for permitting geothermal projects (Hannonen, 2020) and there is a debate, whether these should fall under the building or the environmental regulations. The 2011 Mining Act <https://www.finlex.fi/api/media/>

[statute-foreign-language-translation/124987/mainPdf/main.pdf?timestamp=2011-06-10T00%3A00%3A00.000Z](https://www.finlex.fi/en/laki/kaannokset/2011/en20110610T00%3A00%3A00.000Z), including amendments up to 2023) does not mention any geothermal resources or their use, neither does the Environmental Protection Act (https://www.finlex.fi/en/laki/kaannokset/2014/en20140527_20200905.pdf), nor the Water Act (<https://www.finlex.fi/en/laki/kaannokset/2011/en20110587.pdf>), or the Land-Use and Building Act (https://www.finlex.fi/en/laki/kaannokset/1999/en19990132_20030222.pdf).

Owing to the shallow geothermal gradient in the Fennoscandian bedrock, only ultra-deep (> 6000 m) systems seem to be of interest, although medium deep systems are also being explored (<https://www.egt.ee/media/439/download>).

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

8.10 FRANCE

All underground ore resources are state owned and exploration and exploitation requires licenses (MinLex 2017).

The Geothermal Transparency Guide (<http://www.geothermal.bba.is>) states, that under French law, in principle, ownership of a plot of land includes the ownership of what is above and below such plot of land (Article 552 of the Code Civil, https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/codes/article_lc/LEGIARTI000006428953). As an exception, the exploration and exploitation of geothermal resources are subject to restrictive legislation (contained in the Mining Code). Exploitation of geothermal resources is subject to license in compliance with the Mining Code and Decree No. 78-498 dated 28 March 1978 (<https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/loda/id/LEGISCTA000041414462>). For high temperature resources, exploration and exploitation are subject to general mining licenses granted in principle by the prime minister or the minister for mines (Decree No. 2006-648 dated 2 June 2006, <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/loda/id/JORFTEXT000000790913>).

For high temperature geothermal resources (>150°C) (Decree No. 2006-648 dated 2 June 2006) an exclusive exploration permit (permis exclusif de recherches – PER) is required that contains *inter alia* an environmental impact statement (notice d'impact) indicating (i) potential impacts of the works on the environment and (ii) how the contemplated project includes environmental concerns. The consent of the respective land-owner to use the site is required.

Numerous administrative bodies are likely to be involved – such as:

- The Minister in charge of mines (i.e. currently the Ministre de la transition écologique et solidaire and the Ministre de l'économie et des finances) is the recipient of the application;
- The local representative of the State (préfet) examines the application form and organises the tender procedure;
- The heads of the interested civil and military services (chefs des services civils et de l'autorité militaire intéressés) are consulted;
- The regional environment, planning and housing agency (la direction régionale de l'environnement, de l'aménagement et du logement – DREAL) drafts a report;
- The municipalities concerned are consulted;

- The general council for the economy, the industry, the energy and the technologies (Conseil général de l'économie, de l'industrie, de l'énergie et des technologies) submits its opinion on the project.
- As far as the concession permit is concerned, the opinion of the Council of State (Conseil d'Etat) is also required, and the permit is delivered by the Prime Minister (Article 31 of the Decree No. 2006-648 dated 2 June 2006).

With effect of January 2023 the Mining Code was revised, integrating the mining permits with the environmental permits to allow for a streamlined procedure and ensure cohesive monitoring of the activities (Décret n° 2023-13 du 11 janvier 2023 relatif à l'autorisation environnementale des travaux miniers, <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/jorf/id/JORFTEXT000046971943>). Geothermal projects are explicitly mentioned therein. This also means that only one application is made to cover both mining and pollution control aspects (MTECT, 2023).

Water management is the subject of a framework for water planning and management (Schéma Directeur d'Aménagement et de Gestion des Eaux (SDAGE)). The SDAGE must be taken into account in any administrative decision, meaning that all mining authorisations would need to have regard to the scheme in accordance with the Environmental Code. The relationship between the mining permit and the SDAGE was clarified and confirmed with this New Mining Code (<https://codes.droit.org/PDF/Code%20de%20%27environnement.pdf>).

While France actively supports the development of deep geothermal projects, there have been no changes to the regulatory system by June 2025.

8.11 GERMANY

Regional mining authorities are competent for issuing licenses for the use of geothermal resources, such as exploration licenses (Aufsuchungserlaubnis), exploitation licenses (Gewinnungsbewilligung) or mining property rights (Bergwerkseigentum) (see below). In detail, the provisions regarding the competence depend on the federal state. Prior to making a decision on the application, the competent mining authority shall ensure that the authorities responsible for safeguarding the public interest are given the opportunity to express their opinion. For research activities on the continental shelf the Federal Maritime and Hydrographic Agency (Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie – BSH) has to be involved (EGEC 2022).

According to the German mining law (BBergG, <https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/bbergg/>) geothermal heat is not a mineral resource and, therefore, not controlled by this law. Shallow geothermal boreholes that serve only the need of the buildings on the plot on which they are located do not require a license. However, drilling below 100 m depth for commercial purposes, namely the extraction of mineral value or heat for electricity generation or district heating, requires a license (Frenz 2020). An impact assessment per Immission Law (BlmSchG, <https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/bimschg/BlmSchG.pdf>) is likely to be required, in particular also for the re-injection of abstracted waters. The later would also be regulated under the Water Management Act (WHG, <https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/bimschg/BlmSchG.pdf>).

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

8.12 GREECE

All ‘metallic’ minerals are state owned and exploration and exploitation requires licenses. The Greek Legislation (the Mining Code, namely L.210/1973) distinguishes mineral raw materials into two broad categories: a) ‘Metallic Minerals’ which, either on the surface or underground, do not belong to the landowner, and b) ‘Quarry Minerals’, which belong to the landowner (Tzeferis, 2018). ‘Metallic Minerals’ include (native) metals, all metallic compounds, precious stones, radioactive and energy minerals, sulphur, talc, fluoride, asbestos, dolomites with MgO content >21 %, feldspars, mineral salt, organic sediments, and others, as well as those ‘Quarry Minerals’ that may be treated in order to produce ‘Metallic Minerals’. At the national level, the Ministry of Environment and Energy (YPEN) and, at the regional/local level, the 7 Decentralised (Regional) Administrations (tiers of ministries) and the 13 Administrative Regions (L.3852/2010) are concerned with issuing permits. Who issues which permit depends on the mineral type, size of the project/activity, any land use peculiarities of the area of intervention (i.e. frontier area, protected area), or/and the land ownership legal status (MinLex 2017).

The use of geothermal energy is regulated by the law on *Exploitation of Geothermal Potential* (Law 1475/84). This law asserts that the exclusive right of exploitation of geothermal energy belongs to the state, which, in turn, reserves the right to assign this to other public sector entities. In such cases, these entities have to prove the benefits of such investments. It must be assured that water quality will not be affected and rights cannot be undertaken for less than 15 years (<https://www.iea.org/policies/3971-exploitation-of-geothermal-potential-law-147584>).

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

8.13 HUNGARY

All minerals are state owned and exploration and exploitation requires licenses (MinLex 2017). Thermal waters and geothermal energy are also state owned and covered by the Mining Act (Valkering et al. 2020).

The primary legal basic of mineral extraction activity is Act No. XLVIII of 1993 on Mining (https://rmis.jrc.ec.europa.eu/uploads/legislation/Hungary_MiningAct_ENGLISH.pdf).

Important pieces of law for permitting procedures are Governmental Decree No. 203/1998. (XII.19.) (detailed permitting rules), Government Regulation No. 161/2017. (VI. 28.) on the Mining and Geological Survey of Hungary (MBFSZ), Government Regulation No. 53/2012 on mining construction permitting (<https://net.jogtar.hu/jogszabaly?docid=A1200312.KOR>), Government Regulation No. 314/2005 on EIA and IPPC (<https://net.jogtar.hu/jogszabaly?docid=A0500314.KOR>), Act No. LIII of 1996 on nature conservation (<https://net.jogtar.hu/jogszabaly?docid=99600053.TV>), Government Regulation No. 275/2004 on Natura 2000 sites (<https://net.jogtar.hu/jogszabaly?docid=A0400275.KOR>), and Government Regulation No. 312/2012 on construction permitting (<https://net.jogtar.hu/jogszabaly?docid=A1200312.KOR>). For permitting procedures, Act No. CL of 2016 on the General Order on Administration is also important (<https://net.jogtar.hu/jogszabaly?docid=A0400140.TV×hift=20170101&txtreferer=A1100190.TV>).

Environmental impact assessments fall under the Governmental Decree No. 314/2005 (XII.25.) regarding the procedures of environmental impact assessment and the single procedure of authorization of utilization of the environment (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/hun109029.pdf>). Water-related matters are regulated under the Act No. LVII of 1995 on water management (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/hun5203.pdf>).

Hungary has a considerable geothermal potential (<https://www.ceer.eu/documents/104400/-/-/c1f4719e-55bb-2141-c234-cacc411dba6e>) All issues related to geothermal energy fall into the remit of the water (resources) regulators (Regional Directorates for Disaster Management) if above 2500 m depths, while concessions for resources below that depth are issued by the mining regulator (https://mbfsz.gov.hu/ogre_modul/data/licensing_pdfs/Annex4.pdf). Recent legislation puts high priority on geothermal power production without water abstraction and improvement of reinjection technologies, and also addresses the mitigation of financial risks of geothermal investment (Valkering et al. 2020).

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

8.14 ICELAND

The Geothermal Transparency Guide (<http://www.geothermal.bba.is>) observes that ownership of natural resources, including geothermal, is governed by the Act on the survey and utilisation of ground resources no. 57/1998 ('Natural Resources Act', <https://www.government.is/media/atvinnuvegaraduneyti-media/media/acts/Act-No-57-1998-on-survey-and-utilisation-of-ground-resources.pdf>). The ownership of resources in the ground is attached to private land. Resources under public land are the property of the state. Resources are defined in the Natural Resources Act as “any element, compound and energy that can be extracted from the earth, whether in solid, liquid or gaseous form, regardless of the temperature at which they may be found”.

The National Energy Authority (NEA) is permitted to take the initiative in and/or give instructions for the exploration of resources in the ground anywhere in Iceland, regardless of whether the owner of the land has initiated such exploration or permitted others to initiate such exploration. In the same way, the NEA may permit other private or public parties to explore, in which case an exploration license shall be issued to such other parties. If, however, the landowner holds a valid exploration license, the NEA cannot interfere, and the landowner can either explore himself or allow third parties to explore, without interference from the NEA. A landowner is required to grant exploration license holders unrestricted access to the private land involved.

The utilisation of resources is subject to a license from the NEA, whether on private or public land. This license permits the holder to extract and use the resource during the term of the license to the extent and on the terms laid down in the Natural Resources Act. Before the NEA issues a utilisation license, the opinions of certain administrative bodies shall be gathered. This includes the opinion of the Environment Agency of Iceland, the Icelandic Institute of Natural History, the Marine and Freshwater Research Institute, if applicable, as well as the opinion of the local municipality.

The Icelandic Master Plan for Nature Protection and Energy Utilisation (“Master Plan”) is a tool to reconcile often competing interests on a national scale and at the earliest planning stages. The Master Plan is currently in its fourth phase, which was due to be completed in

2021. All work on the Master Plan focuses on classifying power plant options into energy utilisation-, on hold-, or protection categories. Expert committees established under the Master Plan demarcate the area of impact for the planned power plant construction work and evaluate the value of numerous factors within the area by use of a rating system based on the conditions of the area pre-power plant.

The Master Plan involves to a certain extent innovation and when the work on the plan began there was no fully formulated methodology available that would suit Icelandic conditions. The methodology has therefore gone through continuous development and will probably continue to undergo some adjustments, although most of these will probably be minor.

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

8.15 IRELAND

All underground ore resources are state owned and exploration and exploitation requires licenses (MinLex 2017).

The fundamental law is the Minerals development Act of 2017 (<http://www.mineralsireland.ie/files/MineralsDevelopmentAct2017.pdf>), which, however, does not mention geothermal waters.

It appears that the assessment by Dumas et al. (2013) is still correct and that there are no specific legal controls on geothermal energy development and ownership of the resource is unregulated. According to EGEC (2022) non-specific regulations influences the geothermal activity:

Planning permission (according to The Planning and Development Acts 2000/2021, <https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/2021/act/18/enacted/en/pdf>) is needed for any building associated with the geothermal system and it may be needed for deep drilling.

Mineral exploration boreholes need to be drilled under a license granted by the Exploration and Mining Division (EMD) of the Department of Communications, Marine and Natural Resources

Open loop systems need a Discharge License from the Environmental Protection Agency, especially since deeper systems may produce brines.

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

8.16 ITALY

All underground ore resources are state owned and exploration and exploitation requires licenses (MinLex 2017). Specifically, the Geothermal Transparency Guide (<http://www.geothermal.bba.is>) states, that ownership of natural resources, including geothermal, is governed by the Italian Civil Code

(<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/ita197336.pdf>).

Namely Article 826, para. 2, provides that: “The forests that by applicable laws constitute the forested domain of the State, mines, quarries and turf pits when their disposability is taken from the owner of the land [...] are part of the non-disposable patrimony of the State”.

Article 840, para. 1, provides that: “Ownership of the soil extends to the subsoil, with all that is contained therein, and the owner can perform any excavation or work that does

not cause harm to a neighbour. This provision does not apply to that which is the object of laws on mines, quarries and turf pits [...]”.

Article 1, para. 6, of Legislative Decree No. 22/2010 (<https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/gu/2010/02/24/45/sg/pdf>), provides that geothermal resources qualify as mineral resources that fall under the non-disposable patrimony of the Italian State or of the relevant region depending on the national or local interest of such resources. Only the government of Italy can grant exploitation rights.

The exploitation of geothermal resources is subject to a specific license. Article 6 of Legislative Decree No. 22/2010 of 11 February 2010 (https://www.astrid-online.it/static/upload/protected/Dlgs/Dlgs_22_2010.pdf) sets out the procedure to obtain a license, which entails the involvement of all the authorities concerned (e.g. the Ministry for the Environment, Land and Sea, the Ministry of Economic Development and the local authorities). The license also includes the final approval of the works programme and the geothermal project.

According to article 1, § 7 of Decree No. 22/2010, the administrative bodies involved in the licensing of geothermal resources are the Regions or other entities delegated by the former which are entitled also to carry out monitoring and surveillance activities.

The protection of geothermal energy resources is provided for by Article 5 of the Legislative Decree 181/2023 (<https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/gu/2023/12/09/287/sg/pdf>).

Landowners cannot object against licenses, but the authorities will take note of any opposition and may amend the project in question. Finally, pursuant to Article 15 of Legislative Decree No. 22/2010, the works necessary for the exploration and the exploitation of geothermal resources qualify as public utility, and, therefore an expropriation procedure under Presidential Decree No. 327/2001 can take place, if necessary.

The Regions (Reggione) of Italy also have considerable regulatory power. Thus, the Regional laws of Tuscany and Lazio establish the regulatory framework for geothermal activities in these regions, which are home to most of Italy's geothermal power plants. These laws establish the requirements for environmental permits, as well as the requirements for the protection of local communities and the environment.

While the Legge 8 agosto 2024, n. 115 (<https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/id/2024/08/13/24G00131/SG>) did not fundamentally change the regulatory regime, it implements some of the stipulations of the EU CRMA (CRMA, 2024), namely the acceleration of permitting processes for critical raw materials extraction. No further changes were detected by June 2025.

8.17 LATVIA

██████████ All onshore mineral resources belong to the landowner, who might be the State, local authorities, private individuals, or legal entities. The State has the right to limit the rights of legal and physical entities regarding the land and the subsoil belonging to them by imposing the limitations of the right to use the property (MinLex 2017).

The Law on Subterranean Depths (with amendment up to 2021, <https://likumi.lv/ta/en/en/id/40249>) regulates the extraction of underground resources including minerals and water. However, this law does not mention geothermal energy systems. Environmental Impact Assessment are regulated by the law of 14.10.1998 (with amendments up to 2023,

<https://likumi.lv/ta/en/en/id/51522>). Cabinet Regulation No. 696 of 6 September 2011 on the Procedure for the Issue of Licences for the Use of Subterranean Depths and Authorisations for the Extraction of Widespread Mineral Resources (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/lat174595.pdf>) also regulates the extraction of groundwaters, but does not specifically mention the utilisation of (deep) geothermal waters.

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

8.18 LITHUANIA

All underground ore resources are state owned and exploration and exploitation requires licenses (MinLex 2017).

The main law is the Underground Law No. I-1034/1995 (<https://e-seimas.lrs.lt/portal/legalAct/lt/TAD/TAIS.29464?jfwid=bkaxlrq2>) and its implementing Government Resolutions (No. 1433/2001, No. 198/2002, No. 584/2002), which regulate the exploration and extraction permits. Other important laws regulating necessary permits and licences for the authorisation of exploration and extraction activities include the Environment Protection Law I-2223/1992 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/lit4748E.pdf>), the Environmental Impact Assessment Law No. XIII-595/2017 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/lit181537.pdf>), the Protected Areas Law No. I-301/1993 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/lit180792.pdf>), the Water Law No. VIII-474/1997 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/lit41412.pdf>), and the Spatial Planning Law No. I-1120/1995 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/lit19457.pdf>).

There are no regulations covering deep geothermal systems. The Law on Energy from Renewable Sources No. XI-1375 of 12 May 2011 (<https://e-seimas.lrs.lt/portal/legalAct/lt/TAD/648259603c3b11e68f278e2f1841c088?jfwid=rivwzvpvg>) is more of a policy document. The statement that systems of less than 30 kW do not require a license, implicates that industrial scale systems do, but no more details are laid down in this legislation.

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

8.19 LUXEMBOURG

According to MinLex (2017) the main legislation governing permitting procedures for extraction is the law of 21 April 1810 (last amended in 1994,

https://www.stradalex.lu/fr/slu_src_publ_leg_mema/toc/leg_lu_mema_181001_2/doc/mema_1810A0002Z), the law of 10 June 1999 relative to the classification of potentially dangerous establishments (<https://www.legilux.public.lu/eli/etat/leg/loi/1999/06/10/n5/jo>, amended by Grand Ducal regulation of 10 May 2012) which classifies the extractive industry as ‘class 1’ and makes it subject to an ‘authorisation to operate’ procedure following an investigation procedure called “commodo-incommodo”. Other important laws are the amended law of 19 December 2008 on water (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/lux84420.pdf>) and the Law of 19 January 2004 on the conservation of nature and natural resources (<https://www.legilux.public.lu/eli/etat/leg/loi/2004/01/19/n1/jo>). Relevant authorities are the Ministry of Labour, Employment and Social and Solidarity Economy (<https://mteess.gouvernement.lu/fr.html>) and the Ministry of Sustainable Development and Infrastructure (<https://mecdd.gouvernement.lu/fr.htm>)

which are the competent authorities for issuing the “authorisation to operate” supported by its Inspectorate of Labour and Mines (ITM, <https://itm.public.lu/fr.html>).

Geothermal drilling permits define the development and operating conditions deemed necessary to protect the environment and ensure the safety of workers, the public and the environment in general (<https://guichet.public.lu/en/entreprises/sectoriel/construction/forages-geothermiques.html>). Geothermal drilling permit applications must be submitted to the Environment Agency (Administration de l'environnement, <https://aev.gouvernement.lu/fr.html>). The Water Management Authority (<https://eau.gouvernement.lu/fr.html>) has established a detailed map, that lists the areas where drilling is not permitted and those which are subject to restrictions in terms of drilling depth (<https://map.geoportail.lu/theme/eau>). An application for a class 1 classified establishment operating permit (see above), a water permit, and an environmental impact assessment are needed.

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

8.20 MALTA

 It appears that the geothermal energy sources of Malta are unexplored despite their potential. Malta lies on stretched continental crust which should result in a high geothermal gradient (Gatt et al., 2022). According to MinLex (2017) there are mainly quarrying activities on this island made up largely from limestone. The mineral extraction sector is regulated by the Mineral Resources Act (<https://legislation.mt/eli/cap/423/20150731/eng>), the Environment Protection Act (<https://legislation.mt/eli/cap/549/20230721/eng>), the Development Planning Act (<https://legislation.mt/eli/cap/552/20230526/eng>) when it comes to mineral extraction, extensions to existing quarries and remediation of disused quarries, and the Cultural Heritage Act (<https://legislation.mt/eli/cap/445/eng/pdf>). Legislation of indirect importance to which operations might be subject to includes the Land Acquisition Ordinance (<https://legislation.mt/eli/cap/88/20170425/eng>), the Strategic Environmental Assessment Regulations (<https://legislation.mt/eli/sl/549.61/eng/pdf>) and the Continental Shelf Act (<https://legislation.mt/eli/cap/194/20140808/eng>).

The Subsidiary Legislation 545.35 on the Promotion of Energy from Renewable Sources Regulations (<https://legislation.mt/eli/sl/545.35/eng>) does mention geothermal energy, but does not provide any specific regulations for its extraction.

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

8.21 THE NETHERLANDS

 State-owned minerals include off-shore minerals (shells, gravel, sand and clay of the Continental Shelf – Art. §4b Excavation Act) and on-shore non-surface minerals (e.g., salt). On-shore surface minerals (e.g., construction minerals) belong to the landowner (MinLex, 2017). An amendment to the Mining Act (Minebouwwet), which only applies to minerals resources below 100 m depth, came into force on 01.01.24 and now also includes deep geothermal resources below 500 m depth (Article 2.2, <https://wetten.overheid.nl/BWBR0014168/2024-01-01>). As Article 21.n also makes provisions for using old mine-works for the extraction of heat, one could conclude

that this would apply also to combined extraction. Chapter 2a of this law regulates the permission procedures for geothermal exploration and exploitation projects.

The State Supervision of Mines (SSM) is the agency within the Ministry of Economic Affairs that oversees the production of minerals and Netherlands' continental shelf. The agency is responsible for enforcing mining laws, mine safety, and mineral production regulations on and offshore. Netherlands has a mixed (centralised-decentralised) permitting regime in which the SSM grants the exploration and extraction permits, and the Ministry of Infrastructure and Environment grants the environmental and water extraction permits; however, the consent of the provincial governments is also mandatory whereas the municipalities and local water authorities only provide consultative (legally non-binding) opinions (MinLex 2017).

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

8.22 POLAND

The State is the owner of all on- and off-shore deposits of metal ores (with the exception of bog iron ores), native metals, native sulphur, rock salt, potassium salt, potassium-magnesium salt, gypsum and anhydrite, as well as gemstones (§10.1 of the Geological and Mining Law of 09.11.21, <https://isap.sejm.gov.pl/isap.nsf/DocDetails.xsp?id=wdu20111630981>). §10.2 specifies that thermal waters also are state property, while deposits of other minerals (e.g. sand and gravel, limestone, dolomite) belong to the landowner (Art. §10.3). In order to receive a prospecting or exploration licence, an environmental permit is needed (cf. Environmental Protection Law of 29.09.21, <https://isap.sejm.gov.pl/isap.nsf/DocDetails.xsp?id=WDU20210001973>). The Water Law of 16.09.23 regulates the discharge of abstracted thermal waters and brines, but does not seem to regulate their abstraction as such (<https://isap.sejm.gov.pl/isap.nsf/DocDetails.xsp?id=WDU20230001478>).

The competent authority is the Regional Director for Environmental Protection in the case of state-owned minerals — excluding medicinal waters, thermal waters and brines — and in case of investments located at the maritime areas of the Republic of Poland. Mining licences are granted by the Minister of the Environment for state-owned minerals, but the exact procedure and other authorities involved depends on the likely impact of the proposed mining operation (MinLex 2017).

In Poland, there is no uniform regulation directly dedicated to investments and projects related to the use of geothermal energy. The legal environment of these investments is shaped in particular by sector-specific environmental regulations, conditioned by the level of interference in particular environmental resources (minerals, water), and horizontal regulations, relating to the comprehensive regulation of environmental protection as such (environmental protection law, impact assessment) as well as administrative regulations on investment and construction process in general (construction law, spatial planning regulations) (Szalewska 2021).

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

8.23 PORTUGAL

Land- and mineral rights are covered by the Decree-Law No. 47344 of 1966 and amended up to 10.01.22, approving the Civil Code and regulating its application (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/por210029.pdf>). The primary legal basis for the extraction of state-owned minerals (metals and industrial minerals) is currently Law No. 54/2015 (<https://diariodarepublica.pt/dr/detalhe/lei/54-2015-67552498>). The Portuguese national mining authority for state-owned minerals is DGEG (under the Ministry of Economy) which acts as a ‘one-stop shop’ for mining permits in the exploration, extraction and post-extraction phases. Extraction (mining) activities are subject to a mandatory EIA to be evaluated by both National Environmental Institutions, the Portuguese Environmental Agency (APA) and the Regional Coordination and Development Commissions (CCDR), as well as the Geological Institutions of DGEG and LNEG (National Laboratory of Energy and Geology), depending on the location, dimension and type of resource to be mined (MinLex. 2107).

The regulatory framework for geothermal wells is established under the legal framework of Decree-Law No. 34/2016, which transposed the European Directive on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources. Under this law, the use of geothermal energy in Portugal is subject to a licensing process, which includes obtaining the necessary permits and authorizations from the Directorate-General for Energy and Geology (DGEG), the National Water Authority (ANA), and the Environmental Agency (APA). Also Decree-Law No. 84/2022 of 09.12.22 on the consumption of renewable energy makes reference to geothermal energy.

Geothermal wells are classified according to the type of geothermal resource they use, with shallow geothermal energy systems (SGES) being those that extract geothermal energy from depths of up to 400 meters, and deep geothermal systems (DGS) being those that extract geothermal energy from greater depths.

The licensing process for geothermal wells typically involves a comprehensive technical and environmental assessment of the proposed well site, including the geological characteristics of the area, the potential impacts on local ecosystems, and the risk of contamination of the water table. The licensing process also requires compliance with health and safety regulations, including measures to prevent accidents, fire, and explosion. In addition to the licensing process, the regulatory framework also establishes specific requirements for the operation and maintenance of geothermal wells, including regular inspections, monitoring of environmental impacts, and reporting to relevant authorities.

Water- and environment-related acts are the Water Act No. 58/2005 of 09.12.05 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/por62080.pdf>), the Environment Basic Law No. 19/2014 of 14.04.14 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/por132791.pdf>), the Decree-Law No. 151-B/2013 establishing the legal regime of environmental impact assessment of 31.01.13 with amendments up to 11.12.17 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/por132059.pdf>), and the Decree-law No. 147/2008 regulating environmental damages’ liability of 29.07.08 (<https://www.fao.org/faolex/results/details/en/c/LEX-FAOC081800>). The uses of off-shore geological resources are covered by the Decree-Law No. 38/2015 implementing Law No. 17/2014 establishing the Policy on the National Maritime Areas Planning and Management. (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/por147367.pdf>).

The re-review of June 2025 indicated no fundamental changes to the regulatory system, though Decree-Law 99-2024 of 3 December 2024 aims at shortening permitting times for renewable energy systems including deep geothermal systems to two years.

8.24 ROMANIA

All mineral resources (also including coal, mineral water, therapeutic muds and geothermal resources) and hydrocarbon resources are public property of the state (Art. §1 of the Mining Law no. 85/18.03.2003, <https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/rom73606E.pdf>) and are administered by the National Agency for Mineral Resources (NAMR). The Romanian regulatory system for permits/licences can involve a variety of regulatory bodies and up to 6 permits, licences or approvals may be necessary for both, exploration and exploitation. However, the regulatory climate in Romania in general has been in favour of extraction (MinLex 2017).

Geothermal resources are considered part of the country's mineral resources and are therefore owned by the state. The exploration, development, and exploitation of geothermal resources are subject to licensing and regulation by the National Agency for Mineral Resources (ANRM) and governed by several laws and regulations, including: Law no. 155/2020, supplementing law 123/2012 sets out the regulatory framework for the energy sector, including geothermal energy (<https://www.climate-laws.org/geographies/romania/laws/law-on-electrical-energy-and-natural-gases-no-123-2012-and-amending-laws-no-155-and-no-290>).

Government Emergency Ordinance no. 33/2007 on the organisation of the National Agency for Mineral Resources (ANRM, https://www.ceer.eu/documents/104400/6693346/C19_NR_Romania-EN-Summary.pdf/563d871e-a29e-9998-f847-c05137da019c)

establishes the procedures for obtaining permits and authorizations for the exploration and exploitation of geothermal resources. ANRM is responsible for issuing exploration and exploitation licenses for geothermal resources and is also responsible for monitoring compliance with the licenses and ensuring that environmental regulations are followed. The application for an exploration license must include information about the location of the proposed project, the estimated geothermal potential, and the proposed drilling and testing methods. ANRM will review the application and may request additional information.

If a viable geothermal resource has been identified, the developer must then apply for an exploitation license. This application will include more detailed information about the proposed project, including the expected energy output and environmental impact. ANRM will review the application and may require an environmental impact assessment (EIA) before issuing the license (Law no. 292/2018, https://unece.org/sites/default/files/2021-06/frPartyVI.8h_25.06.2021_annex2.pdf). If an EIA is required, the developer must submit a comprehensive report that describes the potential environmental impact of the project and any measures that will be taken to mitigate those impacts. The report must be reviewed and approved by the National Environmental Protection Agency (NEPA).

In addition to these permits, the developer may also need to obtain permits and approvals from other regulatory bodies, such as the local municipality, the National Water Agency (Administrația Națională Apele Române, <https://rowater.ro>), and the National Energy Regulatory Authority (Autoritatea Națională de Reglementare în domeniul Energiei, <https://anre.ro>).

The regulatory instruments of relevance are the Law No. 292 of 03.12.18 regarding the assessment of the impact of certain public and private projects on the environment (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/rom216015.pdf>), Emergency Ordinance no. 195 of 22 December 2005 on environmental protection (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/rom197188.pdf>), the Law No. 122/2020 amending and supplementing the Water Law (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/rom201282.pdf>).

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

8.25 SLOVAKIA

The legal framework relevant for permitting procedures comprises mainly the Mining Law (Law No. 44/1988 Coll.1 with amendments, <https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/slo43134.pdf>) and the Geological Law (Law No. 569/2007 Coll. with amendments). Other important laws are Law No. 543/2002 Coll. on nature and landscape protection, Law. No. 24/2006 Coll. on the environmental impact assessment (Law No. 39/2013 Coll., <https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/slo183193.pdf>) on integrated prevention and environmental pollution control, and the Water Law (Law No. 364/2004 Coll., <https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/slo182215.pdf>). Competent authorities are the Ministry of Environment of the Slovak Republic, Ministry of Economy of the Slovak Republic, Main Mining Office and the Regional (or District) Mining Offices.

According to the Mining Law No. 44/1988 and its amendments, mineralised waters used to produce ‘reserved’ minerals (e.g., metals) belong to the state (MinLex, 2017, p. 480), which seems to imply that a concession for combined extraction would be required (MinLex 2017).

In Slovakia, the permitting process for deep geothermal projects is governed by the Energy Efficiency Act (Act No. 321/2014 Coll., https://www.mfsr.sk/files/sk/financie/ppp-projekty/garantovane-energeticke-sluzby/zz_2019_4_20190201.pdf), which sets out the legal framework for exploration, extraction, and utilisation of geothermal resources. The act defines the requirements for obtaining exploration and mining permits, including environmental and technical criteria, as well as public consultation requirements.

The Ministry of Economy of the Slovak Republic (<https://www.economy.gov.sk/>) is responsible for issuing licenses for the exploration, development, and operation of geothermal resources. The license application must include technical and economic feasibility studies, an environmental impact assessment, and a plan for the utilisation of the resource. The license is granted for a period of up to 30 years and can be extended by up to 10 years.

In order to obtain an exploration permit, a detailed exploration plan must be submitted that includes information on the proposed drilling locations, drilling methods, and the estimated resource capacity. The plan must also include a detailed environmental impact assessment on the local ecosystem and the surrounding community.

Once exploration has been completed, one needs to apply for a mining permit, which allows the extraction of heat. The mining permit also requires an environmental impact assessment, as well as compliance with technical and safety standards.

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

8.26 SLOVENIA

All metal ores are state owned. The competent authority for granting exploration and extraction rights for mineral resources is the Energy Directorate (within the Ministry of Infrastructure, <https://www.gov.si/en/state-authorities/ministries/ministry-of-infrastructure/>). The local municipalities are an important co-authority as they are responsible for the municipal spatial plans. All areas with a mining concession (or with mining rights) need to be included in the municipal spatial plans and designated as “mineral extraction areas”. For such plans strategic environmental assessment or at least screening is needed (MinLex 2017). Drillholes, deeper than 300 meters require a mining project and this also applies to the drillholes for the purpose of exploration/exploitation of geothermal energy.

Permitting for deep geothermal projects in Slovenia is regulated by the Environmental Protection Act and (ZVO-1, SOP-2004-01-1694, <https://www.eui.eu/Projects/InternationalArtHeritageLaw/Documents/NationalLegislation/Slovenia/environmentprotectionact.pdf>) and the Energy Act (Energetski zakon EZ-1, <https://www.climate-laws.org/geographies/slovenia/laws/energy-act-energetski-zakon-ez-1>). According to this act, the competent authority for permitting is the Ministry of the Environment and Spatial Planning, which assesses the environmental impact of proposed projects. The Energy Act establishes the basic legal framework for the promotion of renewable energy sources, including geothermal energy. It provides a legal basis for the promotion and development of geothermal energy in Slovenia and sets out the conditions for obtaining a permit for deep geothermal projects.

In order to obtain a permit for a deep geothermal project an application must be submitted to the Ministry of the Natural Resources and Spatial Planning that includes a detailed description of the project and an environmental impact assessment. The environmental impact assessment is prepared by an authorized expert, and must include a description of the potential impact of the project on the environment, as well as measures to mitigate any negative impacts. The Ministry of the Environment and Spatial Planning provides guidance and support to project developers throughout the permitting process.

Relevant regulatory instruments are the Environmental Protection Act of 07.05.20 as amended on 07.11.20 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/slv97886.pdf>), the Spatial management Act of 24.10.17 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/slv203422.pdf>), the Decree on waste of 15.12.11 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/html/slv130514.htm>), and the Water Act as amended on 08.05.20 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/slv61692.pdf>).

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

8.27 SPAIN

All mineral deposits and geological resources are state owned (Ley Minas of 21.07.73, <https://www.boe.es/buscar/act.php?id=BOE-A-1973-1018>).

However, the regulatory processes are highly fragmented between the state and the 17 Autonomous Regions, each with different environmental and land-use regulations, as well as different policy agendas. Each of the Regions may enact additional mining rules, provided the basic mining system governed by national provisions is respected. The permit/concession allowing extractive activities depends on the type of

mineral commodity ('mineral sections' A, B, and C). Thermal waters are included under Section B (MinLex 2017).

So, it is likely that combined extraction will fall under the mining law and the respective permitting procedures. For instance, the drilling of boreholes and installations would be covered by the General Regulation of Basic Standards of Mining Safety contained in Royal Decree 863/1985 (<https://www.boe.es/eli/es/rd/1985/04/02/863>).

Spain has a well-established geothermal industry, and the country has made significant progress in recent years to streamline the permitting process for deep geothermal projects. Deep geothermal energy is defined as the use of geothermal energy sources at depths greater than 400 meters. The permitting process for deep geothermal projects is regulated by various authorities, including the Ministry for Ecological Transition and Demographic Challenge (MITECO), the Spanish Geological and Mining Institute (IGME), and regional governments. The process generally involves several stages, including preliminary studies, environmental impact assessments, public consultations, and approval by the relevant authorities.

The permitting process can take several months to a few years to complete, depending on the complexity of the project and the requirements of the various authorities involved. However, there is still scope to simplify and expedite the processes (Arrizabalaga et al., 2019).

In 2019, the Spanish government approved a new regulatory framework for geothermal energy, which includes a simplified permitting process for projects with a capacity of up to 1 MW (IEA, 2021).

Regulatory instruments concerning extraction include the Royal Legislative Decree 1/2016, of December 16, which approves the consolidated text of the Law on Integrated Prevention and Control of pollution (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/spa161835.pdf>), the law no. 21/2013, last amended 09.12.18, on Environmental Impact Assessment (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/spa129010.pdf>), the Law 7/2022 of 08.04.22 on waste and contaminated soils for a circular economy (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/spa209455.pdf>), the Law 22/2011 of 28.07.11 on waste and contaminated soils (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/spa104715.pdf>), and particularly article 57 of the Royal Legislative Decree No. 1/2001 - Water Law - in its recast form of 09.04.22 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/spa28470.pdf>).

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

8.28 SWEDEN

All metal ores are state owned. In Sweden, the right to grant access to concession minerals and permits to extract mineral deposits is reserved to the state. The 'concession minerals' are legally defined and listed in the Minerals Act 1991:45 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/swe42438.pdf>) of 24.01.91, last amended 01.01.06, and comprise metallic ores, a wide range of industrial minerals, coal, oil, gaseous hydrocarbons and diamonds. The Swedish Environmental Code 1998:808 (https://www.government.se/contentassets/be5e4d4ebdb4499f8_d6365720ae68724/the-swedish-environmental-code-ds-200061) of 11.07.98, last amended 01.01.18, is particularly relevant, as permits for extraction must be granted under both the Minerals Act and the Environmental Code. The primary law concerning the extraction of 'non-concession minerals' is the Environmental Code (1998:808) (MinLex 2017).

Deep geothermal projects are regulated (by implication) under the Swedish Environmental Code, and permits are required from various authorities. The Swedish Environmental Protection Agency (SEPA, <https://www.naturvardsverket.se/en/>) is responsible for issuing permits for drilling and construction of deep geothermal projects. The EPA assesses the environmental impact (based on the Environmental Assessment Regulation 2017:966 of 02.11.17, last amended on 01.01.18, <https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/swe187160.pdf>) of the proposed project and ensures that the project complies with regulations related to water, waste, and emissions. The SEPA also consults with other relevant authorities, such as the Swedish Geological Survey and the Swedish Radiation Safety Authority in case of NORM (naturally occurring radioactive materials) that may appear in scales.

In addition to the EPA permit, deep geothermal projects also require a permit from the Swedish Mining Inspectorate (<https://www.sgu.se/en/mining-inspectorate/>), which is responsible for regulating mining and drilling operations. The Mining Inspectorate assesses the safety of the project, including the stability of the underground formations and the risk of earthquakes.

Other relevant regulations are the Land code 1970:994 of 17.12.70, last amended 12.11.20 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/swe202065.pdf>), the Act on the carrying into effect of the Water Act of 1983 of 01.01.94, last amended on 01.01.99 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/swe24831E.pdf>).

Before submitting an application for permits, project developers are encouraged to consult with local communities and other stakeholders to address any concerns and ensure that the project is compatible with local land use and other activities.

It appears that so far, the few deep projects undertaken have not been successful (Gehlin & Andersson, 2016).

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

8.29 TURKEY

The Geothermal Transparency Guide (<http://www.geothermal.bba.is>) explains that Article 4 of the Law on Geothermal Resources and Natural Mineral Waters no. 5686, published 3 June 2007, Law no. 26551 (the “Geothermal Resources Law”), and Article 5 of the Geothermal and Mineral Resources Implementation Regulation no. 26727, published on 11 December 2017, state that all geothermal resources belong to the State, independent from the ownership of the land under which they are located. Although exploration and exploitation licenses may be issued by the State for the operation of geothermal resources, the actual ownership of such resources may not be transferred under any circumstances.

The objective of the Minerals Act, No. 3213 of 04.06.85 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/tur50790.pdf>), amended by Law No. 6592 of 18.02.15 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/tur153084.pdf>) and last amended by Regulation on mining of 11.12.22 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/tur222940.pdf>) is to define the principles and methods of exploring and processing minerals, and to regulate the proprietary rights. Energy minerals, metal minerals, industrial minerals, precious minerals, and liquid and gas containing above minerals are listed in the act. Proprietary rights for minerals are defined in details. Turkish citizens and companies are eligible to explore for and process minerals. Minerals are explored under an exploration license, valid for 30 months. This license

cannot be renewed. This exploration period is followed by a preliminary operational license, which is valid for 3 years and also cannot be renewed. A final operational license is granted to mines having adequate reserves. This license is valid for a minimum of 10 years and is renewable and transferable.

The Ministry of Energy and Natural Resources sets forth the terms and conditions for obtaining exploration and exploitation licenses. According to such terms and conditions, the Special Provincial Administration or (if there is a metropolitan municipality in the relevant province) the Provincial Directorate of Planning and Coordination of Investment of the metropolitan municipality is responsible for the issuance of licenses. The Administration notifies the General Directorate of Mining Affairs regarding license applications and its approval thereof. Where necessary, the Administration may request the General Directorate of Mineral Research and Exploration's to conduct an evaluation of the planned project prior to the issuance of a license.

There are also various other state entities involved in the development, such as for environmental and land acquisition purposes.

There is inter-agency cooperation between the Administration and the General Directorate of Mining Affairs in the licensing process.

Other legislation of relevance includes the Environment Law No. 2872 of 09.08.83 last amended on 01.01.22 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/tur7700.pdf>), the Regulation regarding point source land pollution and soil contamination control of 08.06.10 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/tur130480.pdf>), Regulation on water allocation of 10.12.19 (where mining is mentioned specifically, <https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/tur196786.pdf>), Act No. 167 relative to groundwaters of 16.12. 60 (mining also mentioned, <https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/tur2564.pdf>), Regulation on water pollution control of 31.12.04 last amended on 17.12.22 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/tur89033.pdf>). It seems that the Zero Waste Regulation of 12.07.19 (<https://www.fao.org/faolex/results/details/en/c/LEX-FAOC187824>) does not apply to extractive waste.

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.

8.30 UK

In general, onshore ores are privately owned (landowner), with the exception of gold and silver (MinLex 2017). Pre-Brexit laws and regulations in general emulate EU-Directives and -Regulations, where necessary. Following the European Union (Withdrawal) Act (2018 Ch.16) of 26.07.18 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/uk180139.pdf>) tens of thousands of pieces of legislation that made reference to the fact that the UK were an EU Member State were amended to remove such references and convert them into purely UK law.

The key piece of legislation with respect to mining is the Planning Act 2008 (Ch. 29) of 26.11.08 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/uk89714.pdf>), which is amended by the Environment Act 2021 (Ch. 30) of 09.11.21 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/uk209376.pdf>), and the Environmental Assessments and Miscellaneous Planning (Amendment) (EU Exit) Regulations 2018 (S.I. No. 1232 of 2018) of 08.11.18 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/uk181928.pdf>). The latter addresses in particular regulatory issues arising from Brexit. Other relevant legislation includes the Water Act 2014 (Ch. 21) of 14.05.14 last amended on 19.08.18 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/uk143276.pdf>), and the Planning (Hazardous

Substances) Act 1990 (c. 10) of 24.05.90 last amended on 22.07.20 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/uk75905.pdf>).

Dumas et al. (2013) state that the ownership of geothermal resources and regulations as to their use are unclear.

The June 2025 re-review indicated no changes to the regulatory system laid out above.